

FLAWS - Flow of Water and Solutes in Agricultural and Environmental Systems

WEB Version 1.0 Handbook

FLOWS - FLOW of Water and Solutes in agricultural and environmental systems

Web Version 1.0

Theory and user manual

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Units for input data

Mass=g

Length=cm

Time= minutes, hours or days

Pressure heads=cm water column

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Abstract

FLOWS (FLOWs of Water and Solutes in soils) is a dynamic physically-based model to simulate water flow and solute transport in the soil-plant-atmosphere system. The numerical code was written in Matlab. One-dimensional vertical transient water flow is simulated by numerically solving the 1D form of the Richards equation (RE) using an implicit, backward, finite differences scheme with explicit linearization. As for the solutes, the code solves the 1D Advection Dispersion equation (ADE) by an explicit, central difference scheme, allowing for a relatively easy inclusion of non-linear adsorption and other non-linear processes. The model produces information on the time evolution of (among many other outputs): Soil water contents and pressure potentials in the soil profile; Solute (tracers, adsorbed, volatile and reactive solutes) concentrations in the soil profile; Water and solute uptake and actual evapotranspiration for simulated crops; Deep percolation water and solute fluxes; Root uptake of water and solutes, also in presence of water and osmotic stresses; Water fluxes and related solute fluxes to runoff; Drainage water fluxes and related solute fluxes; Irrigation fluxes computed by the model; Temperature in the soil profile. Compared to other existing models, some specificities of FLOWS model are: 1) integrated simulation of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus transformations and transport contextually to the simulation of water contents and fluxes; 2) hysteresis in the macroscopic root uptake; 3) irrigation management, by allowing to optimize the time scheduling and volumes according to some criterion based on the average pressure head in the root zone; 4) the possibility of running multi-site simulations, which may be especially important for spatially distributed simulations; 5) an interactive graphical user interface, allowing the user to easily handle even large input files and seeing the simulation results by graphical display of the main output variables..

1. Introduction

The movement of water in the soil and associated solute transport have a role of primary importance in many applications in the field of hydrology and agriculture. In the sound management of irrigation water, in relation to specific environmental conditions and cropping systems, knowledge of local water flow conditions in zones explored by the root systems is indispensable. Once the irrigation method has been established, only knowledge of the laws governing water flow allows the necessary irrigation frequencies and rates to be established to optimise the distribution of soil moisture, reducing within established limits the effects of water stress and containing water wastage. Only by studying water dynamics in soil can the contribution of groundwater to water consumption be quantitatively determined. Moreover, the water volumes infiltrating into the soil due to rainfall are strictly linked and governed by the laws of water flow in the soil. No evaluation of water quantities being added to groundwater circulation can be made without first determining the water volumes moving in the zone between the soil surface and the aquifer.

Knowledge of water fluxes, velocities and contents is also indispensable to study the flow of solutes and pollutants and to predict all exchanges, whether chemical or microbiological, occurring in the soil. Within environmental protection initiatives, great weight is attributed to the continuous contribution of solutes characterising any agricultural activity, especially if intensive. Nor should one underestimate the hazards of non-agricultural solute fluxes, and the need to dispose of wastewater, muds and industrial effluent.

To evaluate the nature of the risk represented the presence of these solutes it is important to define the processes governing their movement downward from the soil surface through the vadose zone as far as the aquifer. Only if we know such transport processes can optimal management plans be developed for environmental control with a view to preventing degradation phenomena.

The complexity of such flow processes has encouraged the widespread use in the sector of soil hydrology increasingly sophisticated mathematical models corresponding as closely as possible to real phenomena, which can supply quantitative evaluations also in the presence of highly complex systems, such as soil-plant-atmosphere continuum (SPAC).

In general, such models are based on laws governing water flow and all the physical and chemical processes affecting water transport. These laws have been widely confirmed by experiments and are often reported also in papers in disciplines collateral to soil hydrology (Bear, 1979; Jensen, 1980). Water flow is studied with reference to a porous medium which, on a macroscopic scale, may be considered continuous and in which the various quantities and physical properties are considered functions of position and time. Reference is generally made to isothermal flow processes, to a Newtonian liquid phase and interconnected gaseous phase with a pressure equal to that of the atmosphere. Moreover, due to relatively low resistance to air flow, the movement of the gaseous phase is neglected and only water flow is referred to.

FLAWS is a Dynamic Physically-Based model, written in Matlab, just based on the governing laws and assumptions described above. Specifically, it simulates water flow and solute transport in the soil-plant-atmosphere system by numerically solving the 1D form of the Richards equation (RE) for water flow and the 1D Advection Dispersion equation (ADE) for solute transport in presence of decay and adsorption.

The model produces information on the time evolution of (see figure 1a,b):

- Soil water contents and pressure potentials in the soil profile;
- Solute (tracers, adsorbed and reactive solutes) concentrations in the soil profile. The model also allows for: 1) Simulating Organic Matter decomposition and Carbon, Nitrogen and Phosphorus transport. In this case, carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus transformations are all controlled by the dynamics of the organic matter decomposition and, thus, also by the C:N and C:P ratios; 2) Simulating only Nitrogen transport. In this second case, nitrogen mineralization is simulated as an empirical decay reaction and

independently on organic matter decomposition dynamics, thus without accounting for the C:N ratio in the organic matter.

- Water and solute uptake and actual evapotranspiration for simulated crops;
- Deep percolation water and solute fluxes;
- Root uptake of water and solutes;
- Water fluxes and related solute fluxes to runoff;
- Drainage water fluxes and related solute fluxes.
- Irrigation fluxes computed by the model;
- Temperature in the soil profile

Figure 1a. Schematic view of water flow and solute transport processes simulated by FLOWS

Figure 1b. Flow chart of all the processes simulated in FLOWS, their interactions and simulation options. The model provides all the outputs listed in the lower frame. In the case of multiple simulations (for example spatially distributed simulations or repeated simulations in stochastic frameworks), all the outputs are provided for each of the input parameter vectors, along with the average and variance of each output.

The user may opt for several hydraulic property models: 1) unimodal van Genuchten-Mualem model; 2) bimodal Durner-Mualem model; 3) bimodal Ross & Smettem-Mualem model; Russo-Gardner model.

As for water flow, the model allows to set several top and bottom boundary conditions, both constant or variable over time: potential and fluxes at the upper boundary, potential, fluxes and hydraulic gradient at the bottom boundary. Initial conditions may be given as pressure heads, which can be either constant along the soil profile or variable node by node.

As for solute transport, the model allows for either constant or variable solute application at the soil surface. Also, initial conditions may be either constant or variable node by node. Dispersivity and decay may also be given for each node. As for sorption, the model allows for both linear and Freundlich isotherms. In this case, the user has to input the parameters of the sorption isotherm. The model also describes the solute flow in gaseous phase.

In the case of nitrogen transport, the model allows the user providing several forms (both organic and mineral) of nitrogen fertilizers: 1) Manure; 2) Cover crops; 3) Urea; 4) N-NH₄ and N-NO₃ solid and liquid fertilizers. In this case, the user has to input the fertilization depth (all the nitrogen fertilizers are assumed to be incorporated uniformly within this depth). Organic nitrogen forms are assumed to consist of both slow and rapid mineralization fractions, as well as passive (inert) fractions. The model allows for nitrification, denitrification and immobilization coefficients to be given node by node in the whole simulation domain.

The crop is simulated in a so-called static way, so that the crop growth is not simulated dynamically by the model but the user has to specify the crop development stage by giving as input the evolution over time of the leaf area index, root depth, reference evapotranspiration, as well as the crop coefficient as a function of development stage to convert reference evapotranspiration to the potential evapotranspiration of the considered crop.

With this approach, the model “sees” the crop as a root system drawing water from the soil profile according to the atmospheric water vapour demand and the soil water availability, and as a soil cover which partitions the evapotranspiration in evaporation and transpiration components, and that partly intercepts rainfall or irrigation water.

The model computes internally actual evaporation and transpiration. Transpiration is distributed in a node-by-node root uptake in the root zone according to the root distribution. Several root distributions may be adopted: 1) Uniform; 2) Triangular (Prasad); 3) Vrugt; 4) Logistic. The actual root uptake accounts for either water stress or salinity stress or both and is calculated by reducing the potential transpiration according to a reduction function based on the water potential and the osmotic potential. The user may select different options for water uptake reduction: 1) Feddes reduction function for water stress; 2) van Genuchten reduction function for water stress; 3) Mass and Hoffman reduction function for osmotic stress; 4) van Genuchten reduction function for osmotic stress; 5) multiplicative combinations of water and osmotic reduction function as described above.

The irrigation volumes may be computed by the model according to a criterion based on the average pressure head in the root depth. The model allows the user for selecting several irrigation periods during the crop growth season. Moreover, the user has to input the irrigation depth and the critical pressure head to start irrigation. Irrigation volumes may also be provided by the user. In this case, the code sums up the irrigation fluxes to the natural rain fluxes.

The drainage is included as a sink term based on the Hooghoudt theory for lateral flow and transport to the drains.

The runoff comes from both a Durnian and Hortonian runoff production mechanisms. The model also calculates solute concentrations in the runoff by a physically based model for predicting solute transfer from soil solution to runoff.

The time-scale of the model may be minutes, hours, days.

All the evaluations above can be carried out in a stochastic (Montecarlo) framework, thus providing uncertainties bands for each of the main outputs.

An intercomparison with Hydrus 1D model provides a benchmarking of the FLOWS model.

A distinctive feature of FLOWS is its client-server architecture, which enables users to interact with the model directly through a web browser, eliminating the need for local installation or configuration. The computational workload is entirely handled by the server, which executes the core MATLAB routines, while the client-side interface offers a streamlined and user-friendly environment for configuring and running simulations. The interface is designed to guide users through the setup process with contextual suggestions and warnings, significantly reducing the likelihood of configuration errors. This architecture makes the model accessible even to users who may not have extensive experience with physically based hydrological modelling.

Model inputs—including node and time conditions, soil profile properties, vegetation characteristics, and solute parameters—are provided in Excel format and can be uploaded directly through the main interface. Output data are similarly returned in Excel files, with each file containing a matrix representing the evolution of a specific output variable across all depth nodes and time steps. Additionally, upon completion of each simulation, FLOWS automatically generates graphical outputs—including profiles of water content, pressure head, water fluxes, and solute concentrations—for selected depths and time points, enabling rapid interpretation and quality assessment of the simulation results.

Another key capability of FLOWS lies in its integrated simulation of nitrogen transport and transformation processes. These are dynamically coupled with the hydrological model, such that water contents and fluxes—computed via the numerical solution of the Richards equation—serve as inputs to the nitrogen module at each time step, ensuring consistent and physically based interactions between water flow and solute dynamics.

2. Water flow in soil

One-dimensional vertical transient water flow in this model is simulated by numerically solving the 1D form of the Richards equation (equation 1) using an implicit, backward, finite differences scheme with explicit linearization similar to that adopted in the SWAP model (van Dam et al., 1997):

$$C(h) \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(K(h) \frac{\partial h}{\partial z} - K(h) \right) - S_w \quad (1)$$

where $C(h)=d\theta/dh$ [L^{-1}] is the soil water capacity, h [L] is the soil water pressure head, t [T] is time, z [L] is the vertical coordinate being positive upward, $K(h)$ [$L T^{-1}$] the hydraulic conductivity and S_w [T^{-1}] is a sink term describing water uptake by plant roots, S_r , and/or lateral water drainage, S_{dr} , so that $S_w=S_r+S_{dr}$.

2.1. Hydraulic properties

Richards' equation requires the water retention function, $\theta(h)$, and the hydraulic conductivity, $K(h)$ or $K(S_e)$, function to be known. These functions interrelate pressure head, h , water content, θ , and hydraulic conductivity, K . Several water retention and hydraulic conductivity functions can be selected in the model.

2.1.1. Water retention

Unimodal van Genuchten model (van Genuchten, 1980):

$$S_e = \frac{\theta - \theta_r}{\theta_s - \theta_r} = [1 + |\alpha_{VG} h|^n]^{-m} \quad h < 0 \quad (2)$$
$$\theta = \theta_s \quad h \geq 0$$

where h is the pressure head ($h \leq 0$), S_e is effective saturation and θ is the water content (θ_s and θ_r are the water content at $h=0$ and for $h \rightarrow \infty$, respectively). α_{VG} (cm^{-1}), n and $m=1-1/n$ are shape parameters. Note the effective saturation, S_e , is to be considered as a cumulative distribution function of pore size with a density function $f(h)$ which may be expressed by:

$$f(h) = \frac{dS_e}{dh} \quad (3)$$

In natural soils, the presence of aggregates frequently results in a retention function curve having at least two points of inflection. To represent such behaviour, a double porosity approach can be used which assumes that the pore space from θ_r to θ_s consists of two $f_i(h)$ distributions obtained by equation 3, each occupying a fraction ϕ_i of that pore space (Ross and Smettem, 1993; Durner, 1994; Coppola, 2000).

Bimodal Durner model (Durner, 1994):

$$S_e = \sum \varphi_i \left[\frac{1}{1 + (\alpha_{VG,i} h)^{n_i}} \right]^{m_i} \quad 0 < \varphi_i < 1 \text{ and } \sum \varphi_i = 1 \quad i = 1,2 \quad (4)$$

in which φ_i is the weighting of the total pore space fraction to be attributed to the i^{th} subcurve, and $\alpha_{VG,i}$, n_i and m_i still represent the fitting parameters for each of the partial curves.

Bimodal Ross & Smettem model (Ross and Smettem, 1993):

$$S_e = \varphi_1 (1 + \alpha_{RS} h) \exp(-\alpha_1 h) + \varphi_2 \left[\frac{1}{1 + (\alpha_{VG} h)^{n_2}} \right]^{m_2} \quad (5)$$

$$0 < \varphi_i < 1 \text{ and } \sum \varphi_i = 1 \quad i = 1,2$$

where the following simple one-parameter function:

$$S_e = (1 + \alpha_{RS} h) \exp(-\alpha_{RS} h) \quad (6)$$

describes macroporosity in aggregated soils.

Unimodal Russo (Russo, 1988):

$$S_e = \frac{\theta - \theta_r}{\theta_s - \theta_r} = [\exp(-0.5\alpha_{GR} h)(1 + 0.5\alpha_{GR} h)]^{\left(\frac{2}{\mu_R + 2}\right)} \quad (7)$$

where α_{GR} is the soil parameter appearing in the Gardner's model for hydraulic conductivity (see next section on hydraulic conductivity models) related to the pore size distribution, while μ_R is a parameter related to tortuosity. The Russo water retention model is generally coupled to the Gardner's model for hydraulic conductivity.

2.1.2. Hydraulic conductivity

Mualem's model (Mualem, 1986):

The model is based on the capillary bundle theory (Mualem, 1986) and relates relative hydraulic conductivity, K_r , to $f(h)$ by the equation:

$$K_r(h) = \frac{K(h)}{K_0} = S_e^\tau [\eta(h)/\eta(0)]^2 \quad (8)$$

$$\eta(h) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h^{-1} f(h) dh$$

in which K_0 is the hydraulic conductivity at $h=0$, and τ is a parameter accounting for the dependence of the tortuosity and the correlation factors on the water content.

For the case of the van Genuchten unimodal soil water retention model and assuming $m=1-1/n$, equation 8 becomes:

$$K_r(S_e) = \frac{K(S_e)}{K_0} = S_e^\tau \left[1 - \left(1 - S_e^{1/m} \right)^m \right]^2 \quad (9)$$

For the bimodal case, equation 8 becomes:

$$K_r(h) = \frac{K(h)}{K_0} = S_e^\tau \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^2 \varphi_i \eta_i(h)}{\sum_{i=1}^2 \varphi_i \eta_i(0)} \right]^2 \quad (10)$$

with parameters as defined earlier.

In the case of bimodal Durner water retention, the equation 10 becomes (Priesack and Durner., 2006):

$$K_r(S_e) = \frac{K(S_e)}{K_0} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^2 \varphi_i S_{e,i} \right)^\tau \left\{ \frac{\sum_{i=1}^2 \varphi_i \alpha_{VG,i} \left[1 - \left(1 - S_{e,i}^{1/m_i} \right)^{m_i} \right]}{\sum_{i=1}^2 \varphi_i \alpha_{VG,i}} \right\}^2 \quad (11)$$

For the Ross & Smettem model, the $\eta(h)$ functions in equation 10 are (Ross and Smettem, 1993):

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_1(h) &= \alpha_{RS} \exp(\alpha_{RS} h) \\ \eta_2(h) &= \alpha_{VG} n B(S_e^{1/m}, m + 1/n, 1 - 1/n) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $B(\)$ is the incomplete beta function.

Equation 12 assumes that all pores in the material can interact (Ross and Smettem, 1993). In this case, an instantaneous equilibrium (i.e. instantaneous exchange of water) between the two pore systems is implicitly assumed. Nevertheless, for some materials part of the pore space may bypass the rest. This is the case when for example the cutans on the walls of the aggregates reduces the water transport between intra and inter-aggregate spaces. The conductivities of the two porous spaces are in parallel and, for such independent distributions, the following equations apply:

$$\begin{aligned} k(h) &= \sum_{i=1}^2 k_{0i} k_{ri}(h) \\ k_{ri}(h) &= S_e^\tau [\eta_i(h)/\eta_i(0)]^2 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Gardner's model (Gardner, 1958):

The Russo model for water retention (equation 7) is generally combined to the Gardner's model for hydraulic conductivity

$$K_r(h) = \frac{K(h)}{K_0} = \exp(-\alpha_{GR}h) \quad (14)$$

The parameter α_{GR} is a sorptive number related to the pore size distribution of the medium, with larger values associated with coarse-textured soils. It is also the reciprocal of capillary length parameter, λ_c , ($\alpha_{GR} = \lambda_c^{-1}$), which can be interpreted as the length of the capillary fringe or the air-entry pressure head value.

Vogel et al. modified van Genuchten-Mualem model (Vogel et al., 2001; Ippisch et al., 2006)

Vogel et al. (2001) introduced a modified version of the van Genuchten-Mualem soil hydraulic functions, incorporating a small but non-zero minimum capillary height, denoted as h_e , into the soil water retention curve. From a physical point of view, this approach introduces a well-defined air-entry value, which is associated with the largest pore size through the relation of Young Laplace, exactly as in the Brooks and Corey model (Brooks and Corey, 1966). In contrast, the original van Genuchten model features a continuous retention curve without a defined air-entry threshold. From a numerical point of view, this adjustment reduces the non-linearity of the hydraulic conductivity function near saturation, thereby enhancing the numerical stability of the flow equation solutions.

Above h_e , the soil is considered saturated. As Ippisch et al. (2006) point out, this minimum capillary height (h_e) would correspond to the true air-entry value and should not be confused with α_{VG}^{-1} , which is also referred to as an "air-entry value" in literature and typically exceeds the position of the maximum slope on the retention curve.

In the configuration provided by Ippisch et al. (2006), the Vogel et al. (2001) modification of the van Genuchten-Mualem model, which is a cut-off at the air-entry value and a subsequent renormalization of the original curves, becomes

$$S_e = \frac{\theta - \theta_r}{\theta_s - \theta_r} = \frac{1}{S_c} [1 + |\alpha_{VG}h|^n]^{-m} \quad h < h_e \quad (15)$$

$$S_e = 1 \quad h \geq h_e$$

$$K_r(S_e) = \frac{K(S_e)}{K_0} = S_e^{\tau} \frac{1 - (1 - (S_e S_c)^{1/m})^m}{1 - (1 - S_c^{1/m})^m} \quad S_e < 1 \quad (16)$$

$$K_r(S_e) = 1 \quad S_e \geq 1$$

with

$$S_c = [1 + |\alpha_{VG}h_e|^n]^{-m} \quad (17)$$

2.2. The Sink Term, S_w

2.2.1. Root Water Uptake Sink Term, S_r

The root water sink term, S_r , in equation 1 is calculated in FLOWS according to a so-called macroscopic approach, frequently adopted in hydrologically oriented soil-plant-atmosphere continuum modeling for describing plant water uptake (Feddes et al., 1978; Feddes and Raats, 2004). It is essentially an empirical approach dealing with the root system and needs to be calibrated for different plants and climatic conditions.

The macroscopic sink term strictly depends on two aspects: i) the root density distribution and ii) the roots activity over the root zone during the growth season of a crop. Activity is used here in hydraulic terms, to express the physical dependence of root uptake on changes in the total hydraulic head of soil water, which in turn affect water fluxes to the roots, thus influencing water uptake. In the macroscopic sink term, reduced root activity is accounted for by introducing an uptake reduction function, $\alpha(h, h_{os})$, depending on the local water, h , and osmotic, h_{os} , potentials experienced by roots at any depths along the root-zone. Thus, the sink term is a function of both the soil water and osmotic potentials, $S_r(h, h_{os})$.

Calculating the Root Uptake Sink Term

In the macroscopic approaches to root uptake (Feddes *et al.*, 1978), the potential root water uptake flux per unit depth at a specific depth, $S_{r,p}$ [T^{-1}], is simulated by distributing potential transpiration, T_p [$L T^{-1}$], over the root zone depth, D_r [L], on the basis of a normalized root density distribution, $g(z)$ [L^{-1}], with depth z .

The function $g(z)$ distributes the potential transpiration rate, T_p , through the root zone in proportion to the root distribution (Feddes *et al.*, 1978; Feddes and Raats, 2004):

$$S_{r,p}(z) = g(z)T_p \quad (18)$$

with

$$\int_0^{D_r} g(z) dz = 1 \quad (19)$$

and thus

$$T_p = \int_0^{D_r} S_{r,p}(z) dz \quad (20)$$

Root Density Distribution

In general, the normalized root density distribution, $g(z)$, may be obtained by normalizing the root length density distribution R_{ld} [$cm cm^{-3}$] by its integral across the rooting depth, D_r :

$$g(z) = \frac{R_{ld}(z)}{\int_0^{D_r} R_{ld}(z) dz} \quad (21)$$

R_{ld} may be calculated as the ratio of the total length, $Lr(z)$, of roots in a sample to the sample volume. $g(z)dz$ is the fraction of roots located between z and $z+dz$.

Several root density distributions, $g(z)$, may be selected in the model for simulating the sink term in equation 1, assuming root distributions to be either homogeneous (Feddes et al., 1978) or variable with depth (Raats, 1974; Prasad, 1988; Vrugt et al., 2001), the latter accounting for the fact that in a moist soil the roots can mainly extract water from the upper root zone layers. FLOWS consider several root density distribution functions.

A Uniform distribution over the whole root zone, which reduces simply to:

$$g(z) = \frac{1}{D_r} \quad (22)$$

where D_r [L] is the maximum root depth.

A Prasad-type triangular distribution (Prasad, 1988), with root water uptake at the bottom of the root zone, D_r , equal to zero:

$$g(z) = \frac{2(D_r - z)}{D_r^2} \quad (23)$$

A Vrugt-type distribution (Vrugt et al., 2001), which allows for calculating the dimensionless spatial root distribution, $\beta(z)$:

$$\omega(z) = \left(1 - \frac{z}{D_r}\right) \exp\left(\frac{p_z}{D_r} |z^* - z|\right) \quad (24)$$

where p_z [-] and z^* [L] are empirical parameters. The model allows for nonsymmetrical root water uptake. The non-symmetry with soil depth is determined by the ratio of the p_z value for $z \leq z^*$ and the p_z value for $z > z^*$. As suggested by Vrugt et al., 2001), in FLOWS p_z is set to unity for values of $z > z^*$, whereas the user has to provide the fitted value for $z \leq z^*$.

For the Vrugt's model the $g(z)$ distribution is:

$$g(z) = \frac{\omega(z)}{\int_0^{D_r} \omega(z) dz} \quad (25)$$

Figure 2 provides the 1D Vrugt root distribution by using the following parameters:

$D_r = 100$ cm; $p_z = 1$; $z^* = 30$ cm.

Figure 2. Graph of the Vrugt normalized root density distribution with $D_r = 100$ cm; $p_z = 1$; $z^* = 30$ cm

A Logistic distribution, which gives the cumulative root density distribution:

$$\int_0^{z=D_r} g(z) dz = \frac{1}{\left[1 + a \exp\left[-b\left(\frac{z}{D_r} - c\right)\right]\right]^{\frac{1}{a}}} \quad (26)$$

so that

$$g(z) = \frac{b \exp\left[b\left(c - \frac{z}{D_r}\right)\right]}{D_r \left\{1 + a \exp\left[b\left(c - \frac{z}{D_r}\right)\right]\right\}^{\frac{1}{a}+1}} \quad (27)$$

where a , b and c are the coefficients of the logistic function and z is the depth.

Water and osmotic stress functions

Low water contents and/or the presence of soluble salts in the soil lower the total hydraulic head and may reduce the water fluxes to the roots, thus reducing root activity and water uptake. Reduction coefficients to decrease the maximum water uptake according to the water and osmotic stresses may be calculated independently and multiplied to calculate the actual root

uptake, T_a , as:

$$S_r = \alpha_w(h)\alpha_s(h_{os})S_p = \alpha_w(h)\alpha_s(h_{os})g(z)T_p \quad (28)$$

with α_w and α_s being reduction factors depending on the local (at a given z) water pressure head, h [L] and osmotic head, h_{os} [L], respectively.

Accordingly,

$$T_a = \int_0^{Dr} S_r(z) dz \quad (29)$$

and

$$\frac{T_a}{T_p} = \int_0^{Dr} g(z) \alpha_w(h)\alpha_s(h_{os}) dz = \omega(h, h_{os}) \quad (30)$$

with T_a being the actual transpiration rate and ω a dimensionless water stress index integrated over the whole rooted profile (Jarvis, 1989; Shouse et al., 2011), providing a measure of total plant stress. A value of β equal to 1 indicates that there is no stress in the soil root zone and that the actual transpiration rate T_a is equal to the potential transpiration rate T_p .

When the soil is irrigated by keeping soil water content under optimal conditions, the eventual reduction in root uptake may only be induced by osmotic stress. Under only osmotic stresses, $\alpha_w=1$ and root uptake parameterization is reduced to finding the factor α_s , depending on the osmotic potential (h_{os}) induced by salts in the soil water.

Many of the functional forms that have been proposed for water and osmotic stress uptake reduction comes from the often-assumed relationship (De Wit, 1958; Doorenbos and Kassam, 1979):

$$\frac{T_a}{T_p} = \omega(h, h_{os}) = \frac{Y}{Y_p} \quad (31)$$

where Y is the yield and Y_p is the potential yield (i.e., the maximum yield that would be obtained under optimal growing conditions).

Water stress reduction factor, α_w

Feddes and Raats (2004) reviewed various functional forms for α_w that have been proposed over the years. We mention here two general model types that have been used most often: piecewise linear functions and continuous smooth functions.

Feddes approach (Feddes, 1978):

To describe water stress, Feddes et al. (1978) proposed a piecewise linear reduction function parameterized by four critical values of the water pressure head, $h_4 < h_3 < h_2 < h_1$:

$$\alpha_w(h) = \begin{cases} \frac{h - h_4}{h_3 - h_4}, & h_3 > h > h_4 \\ 1, & h_2 \geq h \geq h_3 \\ \frac{h - h_1}{h_2 - h_1}, & h_1 > h > h_2 \\ 0, & h \leq h_4 \text{ or } h \geq h_1 \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

The figure 3a shows a plot of equation 32. In this model, water uptake is reduced at high and low water contents. Uptake is at the potential rate when the pressure head is $h_3 \leq h \leq h_2$, drops off linearly when $h > h_2$ or $h < h_3$, and becomes zero when $h \leq h_4$ (*permanent wilting* pressure head range) or $h \geq h_1$ (*anaerobiosis* pressure head range). In general, the value of h_3 is expected to be a function of evaporative demand, with h_{3low} and h_{3high} in figure 3a referring to either a low or high evaporative demand.

Van Genuchten approach (van Genuchten, 1987):

Van Genuchten (1987) proposed an alternative smooth, S-shaped reduction function to account for water stress:

$$\alpha_w(h) = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{h}{h_{50}}\right)^{p_1}} \quad (33)$$

where h_{50} and p_1 are adjustable parameters, the former being the water pressure head where uptake is halved. The figure 3b shows a plot of equation 33.

Figure 3. Plots of (a) the Feddes et al. (1978) water stress uptake reduction function (equation 32), and (b) the S-shaped function of van Genuchten (1987) (equation 33)

Salinity stress reduction factor, α_s

Despite the large body of studies on the topic (see amongst others Molz and Remson, 1970; van Genuchten and Hoffman, 1984; Feddes and Raats, 2004; Skaggs *et al.*, 2006; Homae *et al.*, 2002a,b,c), proper modelling and parameterisation of root water uptake as a function of salinity stresses remains a major challenge. The process is mainly determined by the specific soil-water-salt conditions and distributions which become established in the root zone according to the local soil physical-hydrological characteristics. This is why the well-known salt tolerance database presented by the U.S. Salinity Laboratory (Maas and Hoffman, 1977) should be handled with prudence in numerical modelling as most of those data were collected under well-controlled experimental conditions in which uniform salt distribution over the root zone was established. As confirmed by several researchers (Homae *et al.*, 2002a,b,c; Skaggs *et al.*, 2006; Shouse *et al.*, 2011), the reduction function to be used in numerical modelling should be determined by analysing the dynamics of water uptake under transient salinity conditions.

Several functional forms have been proposed for uptake reduction due to salinity (see amongst others Feddes and Raats, 2004; van Genuchten and Hoffman, 1984). The response function can be written in terms of concentration, or electrical conductivity of either the soil water or the soil saturation extract, or osmotic pressure head (Maas, 1986; Maas, 1990; Maas *et al.*, 1999; Maas and Hoffman 1977; van Genuchten *et al.*, 1984).

Mass and Hoffman approach (Mass and Hoffman, 1977):

The effects of salinity stress on root water uptake can be described using the piecewise linear (threshold-slope) function (figure 4):

$$\alpha_s(h_{os}) = \begin{cases} 1, & a \leq h_{os} \leq 0 \\ 1 + b(h_{os}-a), & a > h_{os} > a - \frac{1}{b} \\ 0, & h_{os} \leq a - \frac{1}{b} \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

where a and b are the adjustable parameters, often referred to as the salinity threshold and slope, respectively. The approach mirrors the Maas and Hoffman (1977) model for reduction of yield due to salt stresses:

$$\frac{Y}{Y_p} = \begin{cases} 1 & EC_e \leq A \\ 1 - B(EC_e - A), & A < EC_e \leq \frac{100}{B} + A \\ 0, & EC_e > \frac{100}{B} + A \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

with EC_e being the electrical conductivity of the soil saturation extract (dSm^{-1}). Note, however, that the parameter sets in equations 34 and 35 are not the same: A and B parameterize total yield reductions as a function of average root zone salinity, whereas a and b parameterize local reductions in the root water uptake rate as a function of osmotic head.

Figure 4. Graph of the Mass and Hoffman type salinity stress uptake reduction function (equation 34)

van Genuchten and Hoffman approach (van Genuchten and Hoffman, 1984):

van Genuchten and Hoffman (1984) proposed an S-shaped salinity-stress function in terms of osmotic pressure heads, similar to the approach for the water stress reduction factor:

$$\alpha_s(h_{os}) = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{h_{os}}{h_{os,50}}\right)^{p_2}} \quad (36)$$

where p_2 and $h_{os,50}$ are the adjustable parameters, the latter being the osmotic pressure head where uptake is halved.

The osmotic potential, expressed as osmotic head h_{os} , is assumed to be a linear function of soil solution salinity, σ_w (dSm⁻¹), according to *U. S. Salinity Laboratory Staff* (USSL Staff, 1954):

$$h_{os} = -360\sigma_w \quad (37)$$

360 is a factor to convert the salinity-based values (dSm⁻¹) to osmotic head (cm).

Combined water and salinity stress

A major challenge is how to combine the effects of water and salinity stress. Uptake reductions due to a combination of water and salinity stresses could be modelled by assuming that the stresses are somehow additive or multiplicative. A generalized model for additive stresses is obtained by assuming that water uptake occurs in response to some weighted sum of the soil water pressure and osmotic heads:

$$\alpha(h, h_{os}) = \frac{1}{1 + \left[\frac{\alpha_1 h + \alpha_2 h_{os}}{h_{os,50}} \right]^{p_2}} \quad (38)$$

with simple additivity resulting when $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 1$. Although additivity has been inferred from a number of laboratory and field experiments (e.g., Wadleigh, 1946; Meiri and Shalhevet, 1973; Childs and Hanks, 1975; du Plessis, 1985; Bresler and Hoffman, 1986), its general applicability remains uncertain (Shalhevet and Hsiao, 1986), especially for field conditions subject to relatively wide ranges in pressure heads (wetting/ drying cycles).

Linear or weighted additivity is only one of several possibilities for combining the effects of water and salinity stress. Another approach presumes that water and salinity effects are multiplicative. In the general case this leads to:

$$\alpha(h, h_{os}) = \alpha(h)\alpha(h_{os}) \quad (39)$$

which, in the case of S-shaped curves, gives:

$$\alpha(h, h_{os}) = \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{h}{h_{50}} \right)^{p_1}} \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{h_{os}}{h_{os,50}} \right)^{p_2}} \quad (40)$$

Root uptake compensation in case of water and osmotic stresses

FLAWS includes an option for root uptake compensation, so that a reduced water uptake due to water and/or osmotic stresses in some compartments of the root zone may be compensated by increased uptake in less stressed compartments. The FLAWS approach is based on the work by Jarvis (1989) and Simunek and Hopmans (2008). In practice, a critical threshold is introduced for the water stress index, denoted as ω_c , which defines the T_a/T_p ratio at which reduced water uptake from stressed regions of the root zone is fully offset by increased uptake from less-stressed areas. This is done by multiplying the sink term as calculated in equation 28 by a compensatory water uptake function, ε :

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon &= \frac{1}{\omega} & \omega &\geq \omega_c \\ \varepsilon &= \frac{1}{\omega_c} & \omega &< \omega_c \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

so that equation 28 becomes:

$$S_r = \alpha_w(h)\alpha_s(h_{os})S_p = \alpha_w(h)\alpha_s(h_{os})g(z)T_p\varepsilon \quad (42)$$

When the water stress index falls below this threshold, potential transpiration is partially reduced, though to a lesser extent than in cases where no compensation in root water uptake occurs.

2.2.2. Drainage Sink Term, Sdr

The drainage is included in the Richards equation as a sink term based on the Hooghoudt theory for lateral flow to the drains. It has been demonstrated that a 1-D solution to the flow and transport system, combined with Hooghoudt theory, gives similar results as a 2-D solution with explicit representation of drain tiles based on the previous studies, provided that an appropriate implementation of the Hooghoudt theory is used. This issue has been analysed in details by Mollerup et al (2012).

Figure 5. Schematic view of the system and parameters involved in the Hooghoudt's equation

Water will flow toward the drain anytime the water table is located above either a drainpipe or an on open field drain (figure 5). According to Hooghoudt (1940), the steady state drain flux per unit surface area q_{dr} can be computed as:

$$q_{dr} = \frac{8K_b D_{eq} D_a + 4K_a D_a^2}{L_{dr}^2} \quad (43)$$

where K_a is the hydraulic conductivity of the saturated layer above the drain level and K_b is the hydraulic conductivity of the layer below the drain level. L_{dr} is the distance between the drains. The water table height above the drain at $0.5L_{dr}$ is denoted D_a (corresponding to h in the Hooghoudt work).

D_{eq} is the equivalent drain depth depending on the vertical distance between the drains and the impervious layer, D_{imp} , as well as on the drain hydraulic radius, R_{dr} .

D_{eq} is introduced instead of D_{imp} if the drain pipe or the open drains bottom do not reach the impervious layer. Actually, the Hooghoudt theory for lateral flow to drains assumes horizontal flow lines (according to the Dupuit-Forchheimer theory). In the case of drains above the impervious layer, the flow lines will converge towards the drain (radial flow lines) and will thus no longer be horizontal.

Consequently, the flow lines are longer and extra head loss is required to have the same volume of water flowing into the drains, which results in a higher water table. To be able to use the concept of horizontal flow, Hooghoudt (1940) assumed an imaginary impervious layer above the real one, which decreases the thickness of the layer through which the water flows towards the drains;

van der Molen and Wesseling (1991) proposed an analytical solution to calculate D_{eq} :

$$D_{eq} = \frac{1}{8} \frac{\pi L_{dr}}{\ln\left(\frac{L_{dr}}{\pi R_{dr}}\right) + F(x)}$$

$$x = \frac{2\pi D_{imp}}{L_{dr}} \tag{44}$$

$$F(x) = \frac{\pi^2}{4x} + \ln\left(\frac{x}{2\pi}\right) \quad \text{for } x < 0.5$$

$$F(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{4e^{(-4i+2)x}}{(2i-1)(1-e^{(-4i+2)x})} \quad \text{for } x \geq 0.5$$

The $F(x)$ for $x < 0.5$ converges rapidly for $x > 1$.

According to the solution technique proposed by Mollerup et al (2012), the FLOWS model calculates S_{dr} by firstly dividing q_{dr} in the two components coming from above the drain level, q_a , and below the drain level, q_b , respectively:

$$q_a = \frac{4K_a D_a^2}{L_{dr}^2}$$

$$q_b = \frac{8K_b D_{eq} D_a}{L_{dr}^2} \tag{45}$$

Following the Daisy model approach (Hansen et al., 2012), in FLOWS K_a and K_b are compartments-weighted averages calculated by considering respectively the contributions of all the saturated nodes above and below the drain level:

$$K_a = \frac{\sum_i \xi \Delta z_i K_{0,i}}{D_a}, \quad D_a$$

$$= \sum_i \xi \Delta z_i \quad \text{for all the nodes } i \text{ **above** the drain level}$$

$$K_b = \frac{\sum_i \xi \Delta z_i K_{0,i}}{D_b}, \quad D_b$$

$$= \sum_i \xi \Delta z_i \quad \text{for all the nodes } i \text{ **below** the drain level}$$
(46)

with $\xi = 1$ in the case of saturated nodes and $\xi = 0$ in the case of unsaturated nodes (thus not contributing to the flow to drains) and Δz_i the thickness of the simulation node compartments. The weighted-average allows to account for possibility that the layer above the drain (and that below the drain) may consist of nodes with different saturated hydraulic conductivities. With

$K_{0,i}$ equal for all the nodes in the layer above the drain (homogeneous layer), K_a would be equal to $K_{0,i}$. The same for the layer below the drain level.

Finally, the S_{dr} in each of the N simulation nodes is calculated by distributing the q_a and q_b fluxes over the saturated nodes below and above the drain level:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{dr,a} &= \frac{\xi K_{0,i}}{K_a D_a} q_a \quad \text{for all the nodes } i \text{ **above** the drain level} \\
S_{dr,b} &= \frac{\xi K_{0,i}}{K_b D_b} q_b \quad \text{for all the nodes } i \text{ **below** the drain level} \\
S_{dr} &= S_{dr,a} + S_{dr,b}
\end{aligned} \tag{47}$$

The code requires as input for drainage fluxes calculation the distance of the drain from the soil surface, z_{dr} , the distance of the impermeable layer from the soil surface, z_{imp} , the drain inter-axis, L_{dr} , the hydraulic radius of the drain, R_{dr} . D_a is calculated by the model according to the simulations nodes actually saturated from the impermeable layer upward. q_{dr} and thus S_{dr} are calculated only if $D_a > 0$.

2.3. Numerical solution of the Richards' equation

There exist analytical solutions to equation 1 only in particular cases and in practical problems the Richards' equation has to be solved numerically. In the standard finite difference scheme used by Coppola and Randazzo (2006) and Coppola et al., (2009; 2012; 2015; 2019), the general form of the Richards' equation is expressed as an implicit pressure-based scheme, to be solved for each of the nz (in this code 100) discretization nodes in which the flow domain has been divided, numbered starting from the top boundary of the simulation domain:

$$\begin{aligned}
C_i^{j+1/2} \frac{h_i^{j+1} - h_i^j}{\Delta t} \\
= \frac{1}{\Delta z_i} \left\{ K_{i-1/2}^j \left[\frac{h_{i-1}^{j+1} - h_i^{j+1}}{\Delta z_i} + 1 \right] - K_{i+1/2}^j \left[\frac{h_i^{j+1} - h_{i+1}^{j+1}}{\Delta z_i} + 1 \right] \right\} - S_w^j \tag{48}
\end{aligned}$$

where $C_i^{j+1/2}$ is the derivative approximation to the differential water capacity Δt is the time step (j is the time level) of calculation, Δz_i is the thickness of the i^{th} node, $K_{i-1/2}^j$ and $K_{i+1/2}^j$ are the internodal hydraulic conductivities, S_w^j is the water sink rate (water uptake by plant roots, S_r , and/or lateral water drainage, S_{DR} , so that $S_w = S_r + S_{DR}$). In the case of layered soils, Δz_i is calculated in each layer in a way that a node is centred at the layers interface.

K and S_w are calculated using an explicit linearization, i.e. using h -values from time level j . The approximation with respect to spatial derivative is taken as a fully implicit one leading to a convenient form of solution where the $K(h)$ values need to be calculated only once during each time step, which significantly reduces the computational burden. The same type of approximation has been used in the SWAP model (van Dam, 1997) and by Karvoneen (1988) and Karvoneen et al. (1999). The internodal hydraulic conductivities used in equations 48 are calculated as the arithmetic average between the nodes (van Dam et al. 1997):

$$\begin{aligned} K_{i-1/2}^j &= \frac{K(h_{i-1}^j) + K(h_i^j)}{2} \\ K_{i+1/2}^j &= \frac{K(h_{i+1}^j) + K(h_i^j)}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

The linear system of nz equations obtained by writing equations 48 from $i=2$ to $i=nz-1$ with the appropriate boundary conditions, produces a tridiagonal matrix with the following coefficients:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_i h_{i-1}^{j+1} + \eta_i h_i^{j+1} + \gamma_i h_{i+1}^{j+1} &= \delta_i \quad , i = 2, \dots, nz - 1 \\ \alpha_i &= -\frac{\Delta t K_{i-1/2}^j}{\Delta z_i^2} \\ \gamma_i &= -\frac{\Delta t K_{i+1/2}^j}{\Delta z_i^2} \\ \eta_i &= C_i^{j+1/2} - \alpha_i - \gamma_i \\ \delta_i &= C_i^{j+1/2} h_i^j + \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta z_i} (K_{i-1/2}^j - K_{i+1/2}^j) - \Delta t [S_r^j + S_{DR}^j] \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

which is solved by the Thomas' algorithm.

Flow rates and pressure heads, whether constant or variable over time, can be assumed as the upper boundary condition. Gradients of different value, pressure heads or flow rates, again whether constant or variable, can be assumed at the bottom of the soil profile. For the first and last nodes ($i=1$ and $i=nz$), respectively, the coefficients shown in equations 50 for the intermediate nodes will change according to the boundary conditions adopted.

Flux condition (Neumann condition) at the upper boundary

In this case, the term $K_{i-1/2}^j \left[\frac{h_{i-1}^{j+1} - h_i^{j+1}}{\Delta z_i} + 1 \right] = -q_{surf}$, with q_{surf} being the upper flow rate, so that the equation and the coefficients of the tridiagonal matrix for the top node become:

$$\begin{aligned}
\eta_i h_i^{j+1} + \gamma_i h_{i+1}^{j+1} &= \delta_i \quad i = 1 \\
\gamma_i &= -\frac{\Delta t K_{i+1/2}^j}{\Delta z_{top} \Delta z_i} \\
\eta_i &= C_i^{j+1/2} - \gamma_i \\
\delta_i &= C_i^{j+1/2} h_i^j + \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta z_{top}} (-q_{surf} - K_{i+1/2}^j) - \Delta t [S_r^j + S_{DR}^j]
\end{aligned} \tag{51}$$

with Δz_{top} the thickness of the top compartment (in the case of equal Δz_i for all the nodes, $\Delta z_{top} = 0.5 \Delta z_i$)

Head condition (Dirichlet condition) at the upper boundary

In this case, the term $K_{i-1/2}^j \left[\frac{h_{i-1}^{j+1} - h_i^{j+1}}{\Delta z_i} + 1 \right] = K_{i-1/2}^j \left[\frac{h_{surf} - h_i^{j+1}}{\Delta z_i} + 1 \right]$, with h_{surf} being the pressure head applied at the top boundary, so that the equation and the coefficients of the tridiagonal matrix for the top node become:

$$\begin{aligned}
\eta_i h_i^{j+1} + \gamma_i h_{i+1}^{j+1} &= \delta_i \quad i = 1 \\
\gamma_i &= -\frac{\Delta t K_{i+1/2}^j}{\Delta z_{top} \Delta z_i} \\
\eta_i &= C_i^{j+1/2} + \frac{\Delta t K_{i-1/2}^j}{\Delta z_{top} \Delta z_i} - \gamma_i \\
\delta_i &= C_i^{j+1/2} h_i^j + \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta z_i} (K_{i-1/2}^j - K_{i+1/2}^j) + \frac{\Delta t K_{i-1/2}^j}{\Delta z_{top} \Delta z_i} h_{surf} - \Delta t [S_r^j + S_{DR}^j]
\end{aligned} \tag{52}$$

Flux condition (Neumann condition) at the bottom boundary

In this case, the term $K_{i+1/2}^j \left[\frac{h_i^{j+1} - h_{i+1}^{j+1}}{\Delta z_i} + 1 \right] = -q_{bot}$, with q_{bot} being the bottom flow rate, so that the equation and the coefficients of the tridiagonal matrix for the bottom node become:

$$\begin{aligned}
\alpha_i h_{i-1}^{j+1} + \eta_i h_i^{j+1} &= \delta_i \quad i = nz \\
\alpha_i &= -\frac{\Delta t K_{i-1/2}^j}{\Delta z_i^2} \\
\eta_i &= C_i^{j+1/2} - \alpha_i \\
\delta_i &= C_i^{j+1/2} h_i^j + \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta z_i} (K_{i-1/2}^j + q_{bot}) - \Delta t [S_r^j + S_{DR}^j]
\end{aligned} \tag{53}$$

Head condition (Dirichlet condition) at the bottom boundary

In this case, the term $K_{i+1/2}^j \left[\frac{h_i^{j+1} - h_{i+1}^{j+1}}{\Delta z_i} + 1 \right] = K_{i+1/2}^j \left[\frac{h_i^{j+1} - h_{bot}}{\Delta z_i} + 1 \right]$, with h_{bot} being the pressure head applied at the bottom boundary, so that the equation and the coefficients of the tridiagonal matrix for the top node become:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_i h_{i-1}^{j+1} + \eta_i h_i^{j+1} &= \delta_i \quad i = nz \\ \alpha_i &= -\frac{\Delta t K_{i-1/2}^j}{\Delta z_i^2} \\ \eta_i &= C_i^{j+1/2} - \alpha_i + \frac{\Delta t K_{i+1/2}^j}{\Delta z_{bot} \Delta z_i} \\ \delta_i &= C_i^{j+1/2} h_i^j + \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta z_i} (K_{i-1/2}^j - K_{i+1/2}^j) + \frac{\Delta t K_{i+1/2}^j}{\Delta z_{bot} \Delta z_i} h_{bot} - \Delta t [S_r^j + S_{DR}^j] \end{aligned} \quad (54)$$

with Δz_{bot} the thickness of the bottom compartment (in the case of equal Δz_i for all the nodes, $\Delta z_{bot} = 0.5 \Delta z_i$).

Gradient condition at the bottom boundary

In the case of a fixed gradient (*grad*) imposed at the bottom boundary (any values may be set for the gradient, even if the most used is *grad*=1 to impose a so-called *free drainage*). In the general case, the value of h_{bot} to be used as head bottom boundary condition is obtained as:

$$h_{bot} = h_{nz} - (grad - 1) * \Delta z_{bot} \quad (55)$$

Seepage face condition at the bottom boundary

This is a hybrid condition allowing to simulate the bottom boundary condition in the case the bottom of the simulation domain is open to the atmosphere (laboratory columns, for example). In this case, no downward bottom flux will be observed until the bottom becomes saturated. During the simulation run, the model verifies if the pressure head at the bottom is lower or higher than zero. In the first case, the model sets a zero-flux boundary condition:

$$q_{bot} = 0 \quad (56)$$

Once the pressure head becomes zero or positive, the model switches to a zero-head boundary condition.

$$h_{bot} = 0 \quad (57)$$

Iteration scheme

In solving the Richards' equation, the differential water capacity $C_i^{j+1/2}$ has to be evaluated.

The approximation of $C_i^{j+1/2}$ used in our numerical code is known as the Standard Chord Slope (Rathfelder and Abriola, 1994; Huang et al., 1996a):

$$C_i^{j+1/2} = \frac{\theta_i^{j+1} - \theta_i^j}{h_i^{j+1} - h_i^j} \quad (58)$$

which requires iterations. The iterative process continues until the difference of the calculated pressure heads between two successive iteration levels in each node becomes less than a predefined tolerance ε :

$$|h_i^{j+1,m} - h_i^{j+1,m-1}| \leq \varepsilon \quad (59)$$

with m being the iterative level; a value of $\varepsilon=0.001$ cm is adopted by default in the code.

Thus, for a given time step, the linear system has to be solved as many times as the iterative process requires for converging.

The iteration number required for convergence, $M=m_{conv}$, is also used for setting an automatic variable simulation time step according to the following criteria:

$$\begin{array}{ll} M \leq 3 & \Delta t^{j+1} = 1.3 \Delta t^j \\ 3 < M < M_{max} & \Delta t^{j+1} = \Delta t^j \\ M \geq M_{max} & \Delta t^{j+1} = 0.7 \Delta t^j \end{array} \quad (60)$$

having set the maximum iteration number $M_{max}=10$. Under the third condition in equation 60, the time step Δt is adjusted and the iteration restarted again for the same time step.

2.4. Top boundary conditions for water flow

Flux top boundary conditions: In the case of simulations carried out under real atmospheric fluxes, the upper boundary condition for vadose zone depends on climatic conditions. Either constant (over time) or variable fluxes may be imposed at the top boundary.

Rainfall: In the code, rainfall represents negative q_{surf} . The model allows the generation of infiltration excess runoff either if rainfall intensity exceeds the soil surface infiltration capacity (Hortonian mechanism of runoff) or in the case of profile complete saturation (Dunnian mechanism of runoff). The first condition (Hortonian) is formulated using a maximum infiltration velocity at soil surface, $f_{s_{max}}$ (*fluxsurf_max* in the code)

$$fS_{max} = K_{m,max} \left(\frac{h_1 - h_{surf,max}}{\Delta z_{top}} - 1 \right) \quad (61)$$

where $K_{m,max}$ is the arithmetic average between the surface and top node hydraulic conductivities, h_1 is the pressure head at the top node, $h_{surf,max}$ is the maximum pressure head allowed at the surface (generally $h_{surf,max} = 0$).

In the case of $q_{surf} > fS_{max}$, the code switches the upper boundary condition to an head boundary condition by imposing $h_{top} = h_{surf,max}$ at the top boundary. If the condition $\text{abs}(q_{surf}) > K_0$ for the first node is also verified, the difference $q_{surf} - fS_{max}$ becomes a runoff flux.

As for the Durnian mechanism of runoff, at each time step Δt the model calculates the storage at whole saturation and the actual storage along the whole simulation domain. If the storage difference is lower than a predefined tolerance, $\Delta\theta_s - \Delta\theta \leq \varepsilon$, all the incoming flux, q_{surf} , during the current Δt will become runoff.

Evapotranspiration: In the code, evapotranspiration produces positive q_{surf} . Potential evapotranspiration ET_p is calculated using the reference evapotranspiration, ET_r , method. In this case, the ET_p is calculated as $ET_p = kc \times ET_r$, kc being a crop factor, which depends on the crop type, the growth stage, and the method employed to obtain ET_r .

In both cases, ET_p is partitioned into T_p and E_p on the basis of Beer's law (Ritchie, 1972):

$$\begin{aligned} E_p &= ET_p \times e^{-k_{ex} \times LAI} \\ T_p &= ET_p - E_p \end{aligned} \quad (62)$$

where k_{ex} is an extinction coefficient, frequently set to be 0.5, and LAI is leaf area index.

In the case of bare soil, the crop resistance equals to zero and $E_p = ET_p$. By using the ET_r method, the variable kc is substituted by a single valued soil factor k_{soil} and $E_p = k_{soil} \times ET_r$.

The code distributes potential transpiration T_p over the root zone on the basis of the root density distribution and reduces T_p to actual transpiration, T_a , on the basis of soil matric potential and electrical conductivity of the soil solution (see the section *Calculating the Root Uptake Sink Term*)

The code requires ET_r , LAI and kc , as well as the extinction factor, k_{ex} , as input over the simulation period.

In the case of evapotranspiration surface boundary condition, the code calculates the maximum evaporation, E_{max} , allowed given the difference of atmospheric pressure, h_{atm} (in cm of water column) and the pressure head in the first simulation node, h_1 , as:

$$E_{max} = -K_{m,max} \left(\frac{h_{atm} - h_1}{\Delta z_{top}} - 1 \right) \quad (63)$$

where $K_{m,max}$ is again the arithmetic average between the surface and top node hydraulic conductivities

In the case of $E_p < E_{max}$, $q_{surf} = E_p$ else, $q_{surf} = E_{max}$.

In the case of irrigation, negative irrigation fluxes, q_{irr} , are added to the atmospheric fluxes, q_{surf} . The irrigation fluxes may come either from irrigation volumes actually supplied by a farmer or irrigation volumes calculated by the model according to a criterion based on the average pressure head in the root depth, D_r (see the section below on the irrigation criteria adopted by the code).

Pressure head top boundary conditions: In this case, either constant or variable pressure heads may be imposed at the top boundary. It is especially important to simulate, for example, a water ponding imposed at the soil surface or any infiltration experiment carried out under controlled surface pressure heads. As already discussed above, such a condition also comes into play in the case of initial flux boundary condition, when $q_{surf} > fs_{max}$, and the upper boundary condition switches from a flux to a pressure head boundary condition, with $h_{top} = h_{surf,max}$.

Rain Interception: In the code, rain interception

FLAWS also allows for calculating the possible interception of rain coming from both natural precipitation and sprinkler irrigation. The approach is the same as used in SWAP and uses the Von Hoyningen-Hüne (1983) and Braden (1985) equation to estimate canopy interception, PR ($cm \cdot d^{-1}$):

$$PR_{int} = -a_{int}LAI \left(1 - \frac{1}{1 + \frac{b_{int}PR}{a_{int}LAI}} \right) \quad (64)$$

with $PR = q_{surf}$ (the atmospheric incoming precipitation flux) and $PR = q_{irr,act}$ (the sprinkler irrigation flux adjusted for irrigation uniformity) in the case of sprinkler irrigation interception. The equation for PR_{int} includes an empirical coefficient, a_{int} (cm), frequently fixed at -0.025 for ordinary agricultural crops (Kroes et al., 2008), and the soil cover fraction (b_{int} , dimensionless), which is approximately equivalent to $LAI/3.0$. As precipitation increases, the intercepted amount approaches a maximum saturation level given by $a_{int}LAI$. In any case, the parameter a_{int} should be determined experimentally and specified in the model input (see appendix A of this handbook).

This method, as developed by Von Hoyningen-Hüne and Braden, is based on daily precipitation data. Therefore, daily rainfall must be included in the meteorological input file.

2.5. Bottom boundary conditions for water flow

Flux bottom boundary conditions: This condition (constant or variable over time) allows for water outflow (downward, negative q_{bot}) or inflow (upward, positive q_{bot}) through the bottom boundary of the soil profile. A special case is when $q_{bot}=0$, so that the water cannot leave nor enter the soil profile. This may happen for example because of an impermeable soil layer at the bottom of the simulation domain.

Pressure head bottom boundary conditions: Again, either constant or variable pressure heads may be imposed at the top boundary. It is especially important to simulate, for example, any infiltration experiment carried out under controlled bottom pressure heads. The special case of $h_{bot}=0$ may be used, for example, to simulate the presence of a constant water table at the bottom boundary of the simulation domain. Similarly, the case of variable h_{bot} may be used to simulate, for example, a fluctuating free water surface at the bottom of the soil profile.

3. Solute transport in soils

The advection–dispersion equation (ADE) is used for prediction of solute transport (agrochemicals, salts, heavy metals, ...):

$$\frac{\partial \theta C}{\partial t} + \rho_b \frac{\partial C_s}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \theta_g C_g}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial q C}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\theta D_h \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\theta_g D_g^s K_H \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \right) - S_s \quad (65)$$

including linear and non-linear adsorption, linear volatilization, linear decay and proportional root uptake in unsaturated/saturated soil. In the equation, C [$M L^{-3}$], C_s [$M M^{-1}$] and C_g [$M L^{-3}$], are the amount of solute in the liquid, adsorbed and gaseous phases, respectively, q [$L T^{-1}$] is the darcian water flux, ρ_b [$M L^{-3}$] is the bulk density, D_h [$L^2 T^{-1}$] the hydrodynamic dispersion coefficient, D_g^s is the dispersion coefficient in the gaseous phases [$L^2 T^{-1}$], θ_g is the volumetric air content in soil, S_s [$ML^{-3}T^{-1}$] is a source-sink term for solutes, K_H is the dimensionless Henry constant. Hydrodynamic dispersion is related to the molecular diffusion constant of the substance in bulk water, D_0 [$L^2 T^{-1}$], and the average pore water velocity, $v=q/\theta$, as:

$$D_h = \lambda v + \eta(\theta) D_0 \quad (66)$$

where λ [L] is the dispersivity and η a tortuosity coefficient. However, as discussed by several researchers (Comegna et al., 1999; Vanderborght and Vereecken, 2007; among others) the contribution of diffusion to the hydrodynamic dispersion is often very small.

By introducing an effective dispersion coefficient, D_e ,

$$D_e = D_h + \frac{\theta_g D_g^s K_H}{\theta} \quad (67)$$

the equation 65 becomes

$$\frac{\partial \theta C}{\partial t} + \rho_b \frac{\partial C_s}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \theta_g C_g}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial q C}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\theta D_e \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \right) - S_s \quad (68)$$

3.1. Linear and Non-Linear solute sorption

The model assumes equilibrium interaction between the solution, C , and adsorbed, C_s , concentrations of solute on soil particles. The adsorption isotherm relating C_s and C is described in the code by either a *linear* or the *Freundlich* non-linear equation. The *Freundlich* isotherm is a flexible function for many organic and inorganic solutes:

$$C_s = K_F C^p \quad (69)$$

where p (dimensionless) is the Freundlich exponent, commonly less than unity for most adsorbing solutes and enhanced with decreasing C , and K_F [L^3M^{-1}] is the Freundlich partitioning coefficient (Selim and Amacher, 1997). The *linear* isotherm is a special case where the Freundlich exponent is unity and $K_F = K_D$ [L^3M^{-p}] (the slope of the linear isotherm) is known as the distribution coefficient.

3.2. Linear solute volatilization

The gaseous phase is also considered in the model to account for volatilization and gas phase diffusion of organic contaminants. Actually, even if the latter may decay mostly because of chemical and microbiological degradation, volatilization may be equally important for some substances such as pesticides. A linear equilibrium volatilization is assumed, so that gaseous, C_g , and liquid, C , concentrations are linearly related through the Henry constant, K_H :

$$C_g = K_H C \quad (70)$$

3.3. Solute source-sink term

The solute source-sink term comes from the contribution of solute decay, $S_{s,\mu}$, solute root uptake, $S_{s,r}$ and solute losses coming from drainage fluxes, $S_{s,dr}$:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{s,\mu} &= \mu(\theta C + \rho_b C_s) \\ S_{s,r} &= K_{ru} S_w C \\ S_{s,dr} &= S_{dr} C \\ S_s &= S_{s,\mu} + S_{s,r} + S_{s,dr} \end{aligned} \quad (71)$$

where μ is a first order decay rate coefficient of transformation (T^{-1}), accounting for linear decomposition, and K_{ru} [-] is a factor for solute root uptake, accounting for positive or negative selection of solute ions relative to the amount of root water uptake S_w .

3.4. Numerical solution of the Advection-Dispersion equation

The code solves the ADE equation by an explicit, central difference scheme:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\theta_i^{j+1} C_i^{j+1} + \rho_b C_{s,i}^{j+1} + \theta_{g,i}^{j+1} C_{g,i}^{j+1} - \theta_i^j C_i^j - \rho_b C_{s,i}^j - \theta_{g,i}^j C_{g,i}^j}{\Delta t} \\
&= \frac{q_{i-1/2}^j C_{i-1/2}^j - q_{i+1/2}^j C_{i+1/2}^j}{\Delta z} \\
&+ \frac{1}{\Delta z} \left[\frac{\theta_{i-1/2}^j D_{e,i-1/2}^j (C_{i-1}^j - C_i^j)}{\Delta z} - \frac{\theta_{i+1/2}^j D_{e,i+1/2}^j (C_i^j - C_{i+1}^j)}{\Delta z} \right] \\
&- \mu_i^j (\theta_i^j C_i^j + \rho_b C_{s,i}^j) - K_r S_i^j C_i^j
\end{aligned} \tag{72}$$

As discussed by van Dam et al. (1997), compared to an implicit iterative scheme, this explicit scheme allows for a relatively easy inclusion of non-linear adsorption and other non-linear processes. In the code, the following criterium:

$$\Delta t^j \leq \frac{\Delta z^2 \theta^2}{2\lambda|q|} \tag{73}$$

allows for the stability of this explicit solution scheme (van Genuchten and Wierenga, 1974). It applies for tracers and is thus safe for adsorbed solutes.

3.5. Boundary conditions for solute transport

The equation 72 has to be completed with auxiliary conditions describing the boundary conditions and the initial concentration in the soil profile.

As for the top boundary condition, by multiplying the applied C_{input} (M/L³) by the top boundary flux q_{surf} (and/or q_{irr}) (L/T), one obtains the specific mass of solute, M_s , applied per unit surface area. Accordingly, if one wants to apply a given solute mass per unit area at the surface, the concentration to be used as input concentration, (C_{input} in the code), is:

$$C_{input} = \frac{M_s}{q_{surf} \Delta t_{app}} \tag{74}$$

where Δt_{app} is the duration of the solute application. This equation also allows for calculating the time of application of the solute in order to apply a solute mass with a known concentration solution and a known surface flux.

The code allows for either constant or variable concentrations at the soil surface.

In the first case, the code requires to input the starting time (tC_{input}) and the end time of application (tC_{end}), as well as the applied concentration (C_{input}). Obviously, $\Delta t_{app} = tC_{end} - tC_{input}$.

For the case of variable concentrations, the code requires the C_{input} time by time.

The FLOWS code uses either a so-called concentration- type (first-type or Dirichlet-type) input condition or a flux-type (third type or Cauchy-type) boundary condition (van Genuchten and Parker, 1984) at $z=0$:

The first-type condition may be used to prescribe concentration at the top of the soil profile ($z=0$), as follows:

$$C(0, t) = C_{input} \quad (75)$$

that is, the concentration is specified at the inlet boundary. The ADE solution with this inlet boundary condition provides solute fluxes (or flux concentrations) at any nodes in the soil profile. In other words, the C values coming from the ADE solution with the first-type inlet condition have to be interpreted as the mass of solute per unit fluid discharge, C_f , and the mass flux, M_f [$ML^{-2}T^{-1}$], that is the mass passing through a node i per unit surface and unit time, is calculated as

$$M_{f_i}^j = q_i^j C_{f_i}^j \quad (76)$$

with q being the darcian water flux at node i and time step j . Accordingly, for mass conservation, the integral over time of equation 76 at a node i should result in the mass applied at the soil surface

$$\int_0^{\infty} M_{f_i} dt \quad (77)$$

which for a finite simulation time, t_{max} , may be approximated as

$$\sum_{j=1}^{j(t_{max})} M_{f_i}^j \Delta t^j = M_s \quad (78)$$

with M_s the specific mass of solute, that is the mass applied per unit surface area, t_{max} the time at the end of the simulation period and j the time step counter. The equation 78 is strictly correct only at the nodes where all the solute mass applied at the soil surface is recovered (passed through the node downward) in the time period from 0 to t_{max} . In all the other nodes, the sum in the equation 78 would provide a recovered mass lower than M_s .

The third-type condition may be used to prescribe the concentration flux at the inlet boundary ($z=0$) as follows:

$$C - \frac{D_h(z)}{v} \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=0} = C_{input} \quad (79)$$

where $v=q/\theta$ is the average pore water velocity and the subscript $z=0$ means that equation has to be evaluated just inside the inlet boundary (Huang et al., 1996b).

The ADE solution with the third-type inlet boundary condition provides volume-averaged (or resident) concentrations at any nodes in the soil profile.

In other words, the C values coming from the ADE solution with the third-type inlet condition have to be interpreted as the mass of solute per unit water volume, C_r , and the soil volume averaged mass, M_r [ML^{-3}], at each node i and time step j , may be calculated as:

$$M_{r_i}^j = \theta_i^j C_{r_i}^j \quad (80)$$

The applied specific mass of solute, M_s , may be obtained by calculating the integral over depth of M_r :

$$M_s = \int_0^{\infty} M_r^j dz \quad (81)$$

The use of either first-type or third type boundary conditions may produce discrepancies between flux and resident concentrations. These discrepancies may be quite insignificant in the case of dispersivities values in the order of centimetres (Parker and van Genuchten, 1984). This may be explained by considering the relationship between C_f and C_r :

$$C_f = C_r - \frac{D}{v} \frac{\partial C_r}{\partial z} \quad (82)$$

so that mathematically $C_f \rightarrow C_r$ with $D/v \rightarrow 0$.

However, with increasing dispersive transport over convective transport, the distributions of C_f and C_r gradually diverge, especially at early times and for relatively short transport domains (van Genuchten and Parker, 1984).

As bottom boundary conditions, in the case of downward flow, FLOWS multiplies the flux through the bottom of the soil profile by the concentration in the last node $i=nz$ of the transport domain $q_{bot}^j C_{nz}^j$ to obtain the mass outflow at the bottom boundary. In the case of upward flux,

the mass inflow at the bottom boundary is calculated as $q_{bot}^j C_{bot}^j$, with C_{bot} being, for example, the concentration in the groundwater.

In the case of soil drainage, the mass flux, M_{dr} , leaving each node i at the time step j by drainage is calculated as:

$$M_{dr_i}^j = S_{dr_i}^j C_i^j \quad (83)$$

As for the initial conditions, the user needs to specify the solute concentrations, C_{in} (gcm^{-3}), in the soil water. C_{in} may indifferently be C_r or C_f .

The code allows for setting a different dispersivity, λ , value for each of the simulation nodes.

As for the solute adsorption, the code allows for either a linear adsorption isotherm or a Freundlich isotherm. In the first case, the code requires to input the slope (the partition coefficient) of the isotherm. In the Freundlich option, the exponent of the non-linear isotherm is also required.

As for the decay, a first order decay rate coefficient of transformation, μ , has to be given as input. The code allows for setting a different decay coefficient value for each of the simulation nodes.

3.6. Solute transfer from soil solution to runoff water

In FLOWS, solute flux, q_s ($\text{M/L}^2/\text{T}$), across the soil surface interface is related to the difference in concentration between soil solution, C , and runoff water, C_{run} , through a mass transfer coefficient, k_{run} (L/T):

$$q_s(0, t) = -\theta D_h \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} + v\theta C \Big|_{z=0} = (-\theta k_{run} [C(0, t) - C_{run}]) \quad (84)$$

The equation above accounts for the convective and dispersive modes of transfer between soil and runoff water (Wallach and van Genuchten, 1990). Convective mass transport is directed downward, while diffusive-dispersive transport is directed upward. k_{run} (L/T) is mainly controlled by the diffusion coefficient but it is also influenced by flow characteristics such as runoff water depth, rainfall intensity and duration, surface roughness.

Assuming that C_{run} can be neglected, the equation above becomes:

$$-D_h \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} + (v + k_{run})C \Big|_{z=0} = 0 \quad (85)$$

applying for finite values of k_{run} , from which the flux to runoff may be calculated.

4. FLOWS modules for specific applications in agro-environmental hydrological modelling

4.1. Irrigation

In the case of irrigation, irrigation fluxes, q_{irr} , are added to the atmospheric (rainfall) fluxes, q_{surf} . The irrigation fluxes may come either from irrigation volumes actually supplied by a farmer or irrigation volumes calculated by the model according to a criterion based on the average pressure head in the root depth, D_{root} (see the section below on the irrigation criterion adopted by the code).

Irrigation options

FLOWS considers three options: 1) No irrigation; 2) Irrigation calculated by the model; 3) Irrigation provided by the user.

Irrigation calculated by the model

The criterion used by the model to calculate the time for irrigation and the irrigation volume is based on a comparison between a pressure head, h_{av} , averaged over the root depth, D_r , as simulated by the model, with a critical pressure head, h_{crit} , inducing some stresses to the crop (in terms of yield, product quality, ...). Schematically, the irrigation criterion is summarized in figure 6a,b.

Figure 6. Graphical view of the criterion used by the model to calculate the time for irrigation and the irrigation volume. (a) h_{av} higher than h_{crit} , no irrigation is required; (b) h_{av} lower than h_{crit} , irrigation is required to bring the pressure head at the field capacity, h_{fc} .

If h_{av} remains higher than the critical pressure head, h_{crit} , the average pressure head h lies above the stress condition and no irrigation is required (figure 6a). Irrigation starts any time h_{av} becomes lower than h_{crit} (figure 6b). In other words, it is assumed that stress starts when the average pressure head in the root zone becomes lower than the threshold for water stress. Irrigation aims to bring the actual water content at each depth to the water content at field capacity. At the beginning of each simulation input time (t_{star} in the code), the model calculates the gross irrigation height as the difference of water storage, Δ_{stor} , between the water content at the field capacity and the actual water content in the *irrigation depth*, Z_{irr} , to be supplied on that day. The *irrigation depth* is the depth over which the h_{av} , to be compared to h_{crit} , is computed by the model. The *irrigation depth* may be set at any value even if a reasonable value should be the maximum root depth D_r ;

$$\Delta_{stor} = \int_0^{Z_{irr}} (\theta_{fc} - \theta(z)) dz \quad (\text{cm of water}) \quad (86)$$

Figure 7 provides a schematic view of this calculation.

Figure 7. Graphical view of the irrigation volume calculation according to the criterion shown in Figure 6.

Net irrigation, $q_{irr,net}$, to be supplied on day t is calculated as the difference between $q_{irr,gross}$ and the eventual rain falling at the time when the irrigation starts:

$$q_{irr,net} = q_{irr,gross} - q_{surf} \quad (87)$$

If the rainfall exceeds $q_{irr,gross}$, irrigation water is not supplied.

It is also possible to select an on-farm irrigation efficiency, IE, of the irrigation system used for the crop considered, so that the actual irrigation amount, $q_{irr,act}$, may be obtained as:

$$q_{irr,act} = q_{irr,net} / IE \quad (\text{cm of water}) \quad (88)$$

The code allows for selecting the periods of irrigation during the growth season, as well as the soil depth to be irrigated and the threshold value, h_{crit} , for irrigation.

Irrigation provided by the user

With this option, the model allows the user to introduce the q_{irr} fluxes in addition to the fluxes coming from rainfall, q_{surf}

4.2. Modelling Temperature distribution in soil

Many physical, chemical, and biological processes in soils are influenced by soil temperature and its evolution in space and time. Thus, predicting and interpreting processes involving soil, water and vegetation interactions, also requires accurate modelling of the soil temperature distributions, $T(z, t)$, as a function of depth z and time t .

Temperature modelling along a vertical soil profile is frequently carried out by considering the heat conduction equation (Holmes et al., 2008):

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} D_T \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \quad (89)$$

where $D_T = \frac{\lambda_h}{C_h}$ is the soil thermal diffusivity (L^2T^{-1}), λ_h is the soil thermal conductivity and C_h is the soil volumetric heat capacity.

The equation above can be solved by assuming periodically variable heat fluxes at $z=0$ and that at large depths, T becomes independent on the depth z .

At $z=0$, periodically variable heat fluxes results from both daily and annual cycles. At $z=0$, the conductive heat flux, q_{cnd} , is:

$$q_{cnd} = G = H - Rn - LE \quad (90)$$

where H , Rn and LE are respectively the convective heat flux, the net radiation and the evaporative (latent) heat flux. As for the bottom boundary condition, it is generally assumed that for $z \rightarrow \infty$ the temperature approaches the mean air temperature, T_a , so that $T(z,t)=T_a$. Equation 89 assumes that the change in temperature over a given interval is governed only by heat conduction. Actually, as discussed by Holmes et al. (2008), the convective heat flux, H is assumed to act in a very shallow surface layer, of 0.1-0.2 cm depth. As for the heat flux through evaporation, LE , it may extend to 5 cm below the surface for dry soils. So, to be rigorous, the right side of the equation should include a second term describing the latent

energy loss, at least in the shallow boundary layer where evaporation takes place. Below this layer, the change in temperature is controlled only by heat conduction, as described by equation 89. In many numerical approaches to model soil temperature, this approximation is frequently extended to all depths below the soil surface and equation 89 is adopted to describe the temperature distribution along the whole soil profile. The solution to the heat flow equations proposed by van Wijk and De Vries (1963) represents an early example of such an approximation. The authors described the daily and annual evolution of soil temperature by sine waves of amplitude A_T (°C), varying around an average temperature, T_{av} (°C). T_{av} is considered constant with depth, due to the assumption of heat conservation. Assuming D_T to be constant with depth and time, a semi-infinite soil profile and the following sinusoidally varying temperature at the soil surface:

$$T(0, t) = T_{av} + A_T \sin\left[\frac{1}{2} \pi + \omega(t - t_{Tmax})\right] \quad (91)$$

van Wijk and De Vries (1963) provided an analytical solution to equation 89 as:

$$T(z, t) = T_{av} + A_T e^{z/z_D} \sin\left[\frac{1}{2} \pi + \omega(t - t_{Tmax}) - \frac{z}{z_D}\right] \quad (92)$$

with $\omega = 2\pi/\tau$ the angular frequency (1/d), τ the period of the wave (d), t the time starting from the January first and t_{Tmax} corresponding to the time when the temperature reaches the maximum. The damping depth, z_D , is the depth at which the amplitude of surface temperature oscillations is reduced by e^{-1} and is described as:

$$z_D = \sqrt{\frac{2D_T}{\omega}} \quad (93)$$

in general, the amplitude of the temperature wave is maximum at the soil surface and decreases with depth.

The solution above may be used for either diurnal ($\tau=1$) or annual ($\tau=365$) temperature evolution. For daily fluctuations, the maximum temperature occurs shortly after solar noon at the surface, but lags in time with increasing depth.

FLAWS model uses a combined approach, provided by van Wijk and De Vries (1963), based on the superposition of the annual and daily sinusoidal fluctuation around a constant value of the soil. The approach sums two sinusoids, one for daily and the other for annual fluctuations, each having a constant amplitude and allows describing the daily fluctuations by accounting for the change of the daily average temperature at the surface over the year. Following this combined approach, the top boundary condition becomes:

$$T(0, t) = T_{av,y} + A_{T,y} \sin\left[\frac{1}{2} \pi + \omega_y(t - t_{Tmax,y}) + A_{T,d} \sin\left[\frac{1}{2} \pi + \omega_d(t - t_{Tmax,d})\right]\right] \quad (94)$$

with subscripts y and d used respectively for annual and daily values.

In the equation, the term $T_{av,y} + A_{T,y} \sin\left[\frac{1}{2} \pi + \omega_y (t - t_{Tmax,y})\right]$ represents approximately the average temperature for the day corresponding to the time t , whereas the diurnal variation around this average temperature is described by the term $A_{T,d} \sin\left[\frac{1}{2} \pi + \omega_d (t - t_{Tmax,d})\right]$. With the combined surface boundary condition, the temperature along the soil profile over time is obtained as:

$$T(z, t) = T_{av,y} + A_{T,y} e^{-z/z_{D,y}} \sin\left[\frac{1}{2} \pi + \omega_y (t - t_{Tmax,y}) - \frac{z}{z_{D,y}}\right] + A_{T,d} e^{-z/z_{D,d}} \sin\left[\frac{1}{2} \pi + \omega_d (t - t_{Tmax,d}) - \frac{z}{z_{D,d}}\right] \quad (95)$$

The approach was also used by Elias et al. (2004).

Assuming D_T (and thus the ratio $\frac{\lambda_h}{c_h}$) constant is an approximation of the real field soil conditions. Also, the boundary condition provided by equation 91 is not always a satisfying approximation for soil surface temperature. Finite difference numerical solutions of the equation 89 with λ_h and C_h not considered constant with depth and time provides more flexibility because it may use more realistic boundary conditions (Wierenga and de Wit, 1970; Hanks et al., 1971; Milly, 1982; Horton et al., 1984).

However, when compared to experimental data, the analytical solution in equation 95 provides acceptable results (Jury et al., 1991). More recently, Holmes et al. (2008) evaluated the analytical solution to model soil temperature profiles in a bare soil. They found the commonly used solution to the heat flow equation by van Wijk and De Vries (1963) perform well when applied at deeper soil layers. Higher errors were found when applying the model very close to the surface. These errors were found to be related to the overlooking of latent energy loss in the shallower soil layer below the surface, an issue which also remains for finite difference numerical solutions of the more general heat transport equation.

Figures 8 and 9 provides an example of application of equation 95 to a soil with the following temperature conditions and thermal diffusivity (table 1):

Table 1. Temperature conditions at the soil surface and thermal diffusivity used for the graphs in figure 8 and figure 9

	T_{av} (°C)	A_T (°C)	ω (1/d)	τ (d)	t_{Tmax} (d)	D_T (cm ² /d)
Annual values (y)	12	10	0.0172	365	200	170
Daily values (d)		7	6.28	1	0.5	170

Figure 8. Daily (blue lines) and yearly (orange lines) fluctuations of temperature at 2 cm and 10 cm depth over three years obtained using the parameters provided in the table 1. The orange line and the blue line respectively provide the average daily temperature and the daily fluctuations about this average

Figure 9 provides the evolution of the average daily temperature over time at different depths for the same conditions given in the table 1.

Figure 9. Yearly fluctuations of average daily temperature at 6 depths over three years obtained using the parameters provided in the table 1

4.3. Nutrients transformations and transport in soil

FLAWS model handles additions of fertilizers as organic matter in the forms of manure and crop residue, as well as mineral fertilizers. The model requires the incorporation depth (called z_{fert} in the FLAWS code) as input. It is assumed that fertilizer addition is distributed uniformly

along the incorporation depth. FLOWS allows for: 1) Simulating Organic Matter decomposition and Carbon, Nitrogen and Phosphorus transport. In this case, carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus transformations are all controlled by the dynamics of the organic matter decomposition and, thus, also by the C:N and C:P ratios; 2) Simulating only Nitrogen transport. In this second case, nitrogen mineralization is simulated as an empirical decay reaction and independently on organic matter decomposition dynamics, thus without accounting for the C:N ratio in the organic matter (Stanford and Smith, 1972; Watts and Hanks, 1978, Kersebaum and Richter, 1991).

4.3.1. Simulating Organic Matter decomposition and Carbon, Nitrogen and Phosphorus transport

FLOWS handles additions of nutrients in the forms of manure, crop residue, mineral fertilizers. The model also assumes that manure applications contain 50% of urea and 50% of organic matter (Gusman and Marino, 1999).

Production of Carbon, Nitrogen and Phosphorus from organic matter

FLOWS considers two pools of organic matter: 1) Fresh Organic Matter (FOM) and 2) Stable Organic Matter or Humus (SOM) (Williams et al., 1983). FOM consists of organic matter in manure and crop residue (RSD), plus microbial biomass (MCB). SOM comes from a relatively fast microbial-induced decay of FOM. SOM, in turn, also decays due to microbial activity. The decay of both SOM and FOM produces carbon dioxide (CO₂), N-NH₄ and P-PO₄, which are thus transported in soil in both gas (the CO₂) and liquid phases (CO₂, N-NH₄ and P-PO₄).

In the following, the fate of Carbon, Nitrogen and Phosphorus will be dealt with separately, even if, as obvious, they are strictly interrelated.

Organic Carbon transformation processes in FLOWS

In FLOWS, the FOM decay is described as a first order decay chain according to the approach proposed by Jones et al. (1985) (see figure 10) and used in the EPIC model (Williams et al., 1983).

Organic Carbon transformation processes and pools in FLOWS

Figure 10. Schematic view of organic carbon transformation processes and CO₂ production in FLOWS. Red blocks are pools, blue blocks are rates and the green block refers to the CO₂ root respiration rate. The prefix *r* is for rates. Labels meaning: *fd*= decay of FOM to stable and microbes pools; *sd*= decay of SOM to microbes pool; *mcb,resp*=microbes respiration; *root,resp*=root respiration; *C_{m,resp,opt}*=optimal CO₂ production by microbial respiration; *C_{r,resp,opt}*=optimal CO₂ production by root respiration; *K_{H,CO2}*=Henry's constant for CO₂; *R*=universal gas constant

The rate of mineralization of FOM, rC_{fd} (g cm⁻² d⁻¹) (from now on, the prefix *r* is for rate):

$$rC_{fd} = K_{fd} C_{FOM} \exp(-K_{fd}t) \quad (96)$$

follows an exponential decay according to a decay parameter, K_{fd} (d⁻¹) obtained from an optimal decay constant for fresh organic matter, K_{fom} , which is reduced according to four reduction factors related to the soil temperature, F_T , water content, F_w , the carbon-nitrogen ratio and the carbon - phosphorus ratio, F_{CN} and F_{CP} , respectively:

$$K_{fd} = K_{fom} F_T F_w^{0.5} \min(F_{CN} F_{CP}) \quad (97)$$

The four reduction factors calculations are reported in the following table (table 2):

Table 2. Reduction factors for the fresh organic matter decay constant, K_{fom} (Jones et al., 1984)

Decay constant, K_{fom}	$K_{fom} = 0.8 \quad \frac{FOM_{unm}}{FOM_{in}} \geq 0.8$ $K_{fom} = 0.05 \quad 0.8 > \frac{FOM_{unm}}{FOM_{in}} \geq 0.1$ $K_{fom} = 0.0095 \quad \frac{FOM_{unm}}{FOM_{in}} < 0.1$	(98)
Temperature reduction factor	$F_T = 0.9T/[T + \exp(7.63 - 0.312T)]$	(99)
Water content reduction factor	$F_w = \frac{\theta}{\theta_{fc}} \quad \theta < \theta_{fc}$ $F_w = \frac{\theta_{fc}}{\theta} \quad \theta \geq \theta_{fc}$	(100)
C:N reduction factor	$F_{CN} = \exp \left[-0.693 \left(\frac{C_{FOM}}{N_{FOM} + N_{IN}} - 25 \right) / 25 \right]$	(101)
C:P reduction factor	$F_{CP} = \exp \left[-0.693 \left(\frac{C_{FOM}}{P_{FOM} + P_{IN}} - 200 \right) / 200 \right]$	(102)

In table 2, θ and θ_{fc} are the actual water content and the water content at field capacity, C_{FOM} , N_{FOM} , P_{FOM} (g cm^{-2}) are the carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus content of the FOM, N_{IN} and P_{IN} (g cm^{-2}) are the nitrogen and the phosphorus contents from inorganic sources (mineral fertilizers). All the organic matter transformations are assumed to involve the whole FOM in soil. Thus, all the reduction factors in table 2 are calculated as averages in the whole incorporation depth, Z_{fert} .

Following the approach proposed by Jones et al. (1985), FLOWS assumes that about 20 percent of the carbon contained in the FOM, C_{FOM} , coming from the carbon in the microbial mass, C_{MCB} , and that in the residuals, C_{RSD} , mineralizes rapidly at a rate appropriate to non-structural carbohydrates. According to the same approach, about 70 percent of the residue mineralizes more slowly at a rate typical of cellulose-like materials, whereas the remaining 10 percent decomposes even more slowly at a rate appropriate to lignin. Accordingly, K_{fom} assumes a different value depending on the ratio of the FOM to be still unmineralized, FOM_{unm} , to the initial FOM, FOM_{in} , in the fertilization depth, Z_{fert} (see equation 98 in table 2).

About 20 percent of the carbon coming from mineralization ($0.2 rC_{fd}$) is incorporated into the stable organic matter (C_{SOM}) (the humus pool). The remaining ($0.8 rC_{fd}$) goes to the microbes' pool and will be partly respired (see below).

The carbon in C_{SOM} , in turn, will mineralize according to a first order rate constant, K_{sd} :

$$rC_{sd} = K_{sd}C_{FOM} \exp(-K_{sd}t) \quad (103)$$

The carbon mineralized from the C_{SOM} will cumulate to that coming from the FOM and will follow the same fate. Partly, the total mineralized carbon will be used by the microbes (rC_{mcb}) and partly will go to CO_2 by microbial respiration at a rate $rC_{mcb,rsp}$.

Microbial and Root respiration

FLAWS calculates microbial respiration, $rC_{mcb,rsp}$, and root respiration, $rC_{root,rsp}$ in a similar way, by following the approach proposed by Šimunek and Suarez (1993).

FLAWS considers only the production of CO_2 from microbial and root respiration, whereas neglects that coming from other chemical reactions with soil organic and mineral components, by assuming them of relatively minor importance for CO_2 balance in soil. According to Šimunek and Suarez (1993), optimal CO_2 production coming from microbial respiration, $rC_{m,rsp,opt}$ ($g\ cm^{-2}\ d^{-1}$), and root respiration, $rC_{r,rsp,opt}$ ($g\ cm^{-2}\ d^{-1}$), is assumed to be a function of soil depth and is affected by water content (or pressure head), temperature, pre-existing CO_2 concentration in soil. Both the diurnal and seasonal influences are assumed to be already accounted for by the effect of the temperature.

Thus, the microbial and root respiration ($g\ cm^{-3}\ d^{-1}$) are calculated by equations 104 and 105, respectively:

$$rC_{mcb,rsp} = rC_{m,rsp,opt}f(z)f(h)f(T)f(CO_2) \quad (104)$$

$$rC_{root,rsp} = rC_{r,rsp,opt}f(z)f(h)f(T)f(CO_2) \quad (105)$$

The equations for calculating the factors in equation 104 and 105 are summarised in table 3.

Table 3. Equations for calculation of the factors for the dependence of microbial (equation 104) and root (equation 105) respiration on soil depth (z), pressure head (h), temperature (T) and CO_2 concentration (Šimůnek and Suarez, 1993)

Depth dependence, $f(z)$ (cm^{-1})	$f(z) = g(z)$	(106)
Water content (pressure head) dependence, $f(h)$ (dimensionless)	$f(h) = \frac{\log h - \log h_1 }{\log h_2 - \log h_1 }$	$h_1 < h < h_2$
	$f(h) = \frac{\log h - \log h_3 }{\log h_2 - \log h_3 }$	$h_2 < h < h_3$
	$f(h) = 0$	$h < h_3; h > h_1$
Temperature dependence, $f(T)$ (dimensionless)	$f(T) = \exp \left[\frac{E(T - T_{20})}{RTT_{20}} \right]$	(108)
CO_2 dependence on its own concentration, $f(CO_2)$ (dimensionless)	$f(CO_2) = \frac{0.21C_{CO_2,g}}{0.42 - C_{CO_2,g} - K_M^*}$	(109)

with $g(z)$ being the root distribution function (see section 2.2.1), $C_{CO_2,g}$ the concentration of CO_2 in the gas phase, $K_M^* = 0.21 - K_M$, with K_M the Michaelis-Menten constant, R the universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$), T the absolute temperature ($^{\circ}C + 273.15$), $T_{20}=293.15\text{K}$ and E the activation energy for the reaction. According to Suarez and Šimůnek (1993), FLOWS assumes $K_M^* = 0.19 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $E=5000 \text{ J mol}^{-1}$, the pressure head for optimal soil respiration, $h_2 = -100\text{cm}$ in water column, the pressure head when respiration ceases, $h_3 = -10^7\text{cm}$ and the pressure head when the soil is in close-to-saturation (anaerobiosis point), $h_1 =$ air entry pressure head. Note that T_{20} is the temperature when $f(T)=1$. For $T > T_{20}$ $f(T) > 1$ and for $T < T_{20}$ $f(T) < 1$.

FLOWS uses a default value of $0.00036 \text{ g cm}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ for $rC_{r,resp,opt}$, corresponding to the value of $0.002 \text{ m}^3 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ suggested by Suarez and Simunek, 1993 and assuming carbon dioxide weight $0.001836 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ (at the pressure of $1 \text{ atm} = 101325 \text{ Pa}$ and temperature of $25^{\circ}C$). As for optimal microbial respiration, FLOWS assumes $rC_{m,resp,opt} = 0.4 rC_{fsm} + 0.6 rC_{sm}$.

In fact, given an average Carbon Use Efficiency of 0.4 (Jones et al, 1983; Spohn et al., 2016), 0.4 of rC_{sm} and 0.32 of C_{fsm} (0.4 of $0.8 C_{fsm}$) should be used to build the microbial biomass (immobilization), while the complement to 1 of rC_{sm} (0.6) and of rC_{fsm} (0.48) should be used for microbial respiration. In FLOWS, the immobilized C adds to the microbial pool (C_{MCB}) and thus to the fresh organic matter (C_{FOM}) pool.

The respiration from roots and microbes are assumed to be additive, so that the production rate of CO₂ coming from respiration (rC_{CO_2}) (g cm⁻³ d⁻¹) is:

$$rC_{CO_2} = rC_{mcb,rsp} + rC_{root,rsp} \quad (110)$$

rC_{CO_2} will partly pass to liquid phase, C_{liq} , according to the following equation:

$$C_{liq} = \frac{rC_{CO_2}}{K_{H,CO_2}} \quad (111)$$

while the residual part, C_{gas} , will remain in gas phase. Both are passed to the ADE for transport process. Both C_{liq} and C_{gas} will be in g cm⁻² d⁻¹. They are thus divided by the incorporation depth, z_{fert} , to obtain the concentrations in each calculation node in g cm⁻³ d⁻¹ required by the ADE.

In equation 111, K_{H,CO_2} is the Henry's constant for CO₂ (dimensionless). It is obtained as (Sander, 2015).

$$\begin{aligned} K_{H,CO_2} &= \frac{1}{H_{cc}} = \frac{C_{gas}}{C_{liq}} \\ H_{cc} &= H_{cp}RT \\ H_{cp} &= \frac{C_{liq}}{p} \end{aligned} \quad (112)$$

with H_{cp} the Henry solubility (mol m⁻³ Pa⁻¹), expressed as the ratio of the concentration of a species in the liquid (aqueous) phase and the partial pressure, p (Pa) of that species in the gas phase under equilibrium conditions. For the CO₂, H_{cp} is 0.00034 mol m⁻³ Pa⁻¹ (see table 6 in Sander, 2015). H_{cc} is the dimensionless Henry solubility, R is the gas constant (8.314 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹) and T the absolute temperature (°C + 273.15).

Organic Nitrogen and Phosphorus transformation processes in FLOWS

Organic Nitrogen and Phosphorus are introduced in FLOWS by a fertilizers table. The organic nitrogen and phosphorus transformations considered in FLOWS are summarised schematically in figure 11 and figure 12, respectively.

Organic Nitrogen transformation processes and pools in FLOWS

Liquid Phase Nitrogen transformation process constants and pools in FLOWS

Figure 11. Schematic view of organic and mineral nitrogen transformation processes in FLOWS. The mineralization follows exactly the same paths already seen for organic carbon, with nitrogen mineralization proportional to that of the carbon. Constants K_{fd} and K_{sd} are the same as for carbon. The prefix r is for rates. The nitrogen immobilization in the microbial pool is regulated by the C:N ratio in the microbes ($CN_{ratio,mcb}$), which, according to Cleveland and Liptzin (2007), is assumed to be 8.5. The meaning of pools and constants is given in the text

Organic Phosphorus transformation processes and pools in FLOWS

Liquid Phase Phosphorus transformation process constants and pools in FLOWS

Figure 12. Schematic view of organic and mineral phosphorus transformation processes in FLOWS. The mineralization follows the same paths already seen for organic carbon, with phosphorus mineralization proportional to that of the carbon. Constants K_{fd} and K_{sd} are the same as for carbon. The prefix r is for rates. The phosphorus immobilization in the microbial pool is regulated by the C:P ratio in the microbes ($CP_{ratio,mcb}$), which, according to Cleveland and Liptzin (2007), is assumed to be 60. The meaning of pools and constants is given in the text

In FLOWS, organic nitrogen and phosphorus mineralization follows the same path of the carbon and the immobilization rates (rN_{mcb} and rP_{mcb}) are proportional to that of the carbon according to C:N and the C:P ratios of the microbial mass in soil, which are assumed to be about 8.5 and 60, respectively (see Cleveland and Liptzin, 2007):

Nitrogen immobilization (compare figures 10 and 11)	$rN_{mcb} = \frac{rC_{mcb}}{CN_{ratio,mcb}}$	(113)
Phosphorus immobilization (compare figures 10 and 12)	$rP_{mcb} = \frac{rC_{mcb}}{CP_{ratio,mcb}}$	(114)

In other words, N and P mineralize according to equation 96, with C_{FOM} replaced by N_{FOM} and P_{FOM} , respectively. Likewise, N_{SOM} and P_{SOM} decay according to equation 103.

The nitrogen (N-NH₄ and N-NO₃) and phosphorus (P-PO₄) coming from organic mineralization enter into the mineral N-NH₄ and N-NO₃ and P-PO₄ pools and add to that eventually coming from mineral fertilizers, which for nitrogen can be urea (UREA_{FERT}), as well as solid and liquid NH₄ and NO₃ fertilizers (S&L_NH₄_{FERT}, S&L_NO₃_{FERT}) sources; for phosphorus, solid and liquid PO₄ fertilizers (S&L_PO₄_{FERT}).

The subsequent fate of these different pools of mineral N-NH₄ and N-NO₃ and P-PO₄ is determined by different transformation reactions, frequently described as first-order decay, each with a specific constant, as well as by transport.

As for nitrogen, urea is hydrolysed according to a first-order decay with a constant k_{hyd} , producing NH₄. Part of this volatilizes according to a decay constant k_{vol} :

Urea hydrolysis and ammonium volatilization (Liang et al., 2007)	$\begin{aligned} rNH4_{hUR} &= UR_0 K_{hyd} \exp(-k_{hyd}t) \\ rNH3_{vUR} &= NH4_{hUR} K_{vol} \exp(-k_{vol}t) \end{aligned}$	(115)
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where UR_0 is the initial urea concentration, and k_{hUR} and k_{vUR} are the first-order rate coefficients for the two decay reactions (hydrolysis and volatilization, respectively).

Beside immobilization, N-NH₄ and N-NO₃ in the soil solution (N-NH₄_{liq} and N-NO₃_{liq}) phase may undergo nitrification (k_{nitr}) and denitrification (k_{den}), respectively. N-NH₄ may also be adsorbed to the solid fraction of the soil according to a linear isotherm with coefficient of distribution k_{ads} . Finally, soil N-NH₄ and N-NO₃ may be drawn by root uptake and/or artificial drainage (both unified under a sink term, labelled by subscript UD).

The remaining N-NH₄ and N-NO₃ concentrations are thus transported through soil by advection-dispersion (subscript *transp* in figures 11). Accordingly, for nitrogen transport, the advection-dispersion equation (ADE) is used twice:

$$\frac{\partial \theta C_{NH}}{\partial t} + \rho_b \frac{\partial C_{a,NH}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial q C_{NH}}{\partial z} + \frac{(\partial \theta D \frac{\partial C_{NH}}{\partial z})}{\partial z} - S_{S_{NH}} \quad (116)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta C_{NO}}{\partial t} + \rho_b \frac{\partial C_{a,NO}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial q C_{NO}}{\partial z} + \frac{\left(\partial \theta D \frac{\partial C_{NO}}{\partial z} \right)}{\partial z} - S_{SNO} \quad (117)$$

The subscripts NH and NO are for ammonium, N-NH₄, and nitrates, N-NO₃, forms of nitrogen, respectively. We assume here that both N-NH₄ and N-NO₃ may be adsorbed to the solid phase (the N-NO₃ on a positively charged surface). Note that the two equations are linked through the nitrification process which transforms part of the N-NH₄ (a sink for equation 116) to N-NO₃ (a source for the equation 117).

Specifically, S_{SNH} and S_{SNO} in the equations 116 and 117 are the source-sink terms of solute, all function of depth z and time t , and can be written respectively as:

$$S_{SNH} = -S_{SminNH} - S_{Surea} - S_{SfrtNH} + S_{Snit} + S_{Svol} + S_{SupNH} + S_{SdrNH} \quad (118)$$

$$S_{SNO} = -S_{Snit} - S_{SfrtNO} + S_{Sden} + S_{SupNO} + S_{SdrNO}$$

where S_{SminNH} and S_{Surea} are the N-NH₄ coming from mineralization (see equation 96) and urea hydrolysis (see equations 115), respectively, S_{Snit} is the N-NH₄ transformed by nitrification, S_{Simm} is the immobilized N-NO₃. S_{Sden} and S_{Svol} are the N-NO₃ and the N-NH₄ lost by denitrification and volatilization, respectively. S_{SupNH} and S_{SupNO} are the N-NH₄ and N-NO₃ root uptake, respectively. Likewise, S_{SdrNH} and S_{SdrNO} refer to the N-NH₄ and N-NO₃ losses through the artificial drainage.

Finally, S_{SfrtNH} and S_{SfrtNO} are the N-NH₄ and N-NO₃ source terms coming from mineral fertilizers additions (other than urea).

The source terms S_{SminNH} , S_{Surea} , S_{SfrtNH} , and S_{SfrtNO} , are obtained by dividing the mineralization, urea hydrolysis and mineral fertilizer addition rates (all in g/cm² of soil per day) by the incorporation depth, z_{fert} (cm), to obtain the corresponding S_s terms (in g/cm³ of soil per day) to be added to each of the calculation nodes within z_{fert} .

Table 4 summarises the equations controlling the liquid phase nitrogen transformation processes considered in FLOWS and also schematically illustrated in the figure 11 in the block about *Liquid phase nitrogen transformation process constants and pools in FLOWS*.

Table 4. The nitrogen transformation processes implemented in FLOWS. In the table, the S_s rates are in g/cm^3 of soil per day

Urea hydrolysis	$SS_{urea} = rNH4_{hUR}$	See equations (115)
Urea volatilization	$SS_{vol} = rNH3_{vUR}$	
Nitrification (Cabon et al., 1991)	$SS_{nit} = k_{nit} \times 1.07^{(T-T_{opt})} \frac{\theta}{\theta_{fc}} C_{NH} \quad \theta \leq \theta_{fc}$ $SS_{nit} = k_{nit} \times 1.07^{(T-T_{opt})} \frac{\theta_{fc}}{\theta} C_{NH} \quad \theta > \theta_{fc}$	(119)
Denitrification (Lafolie, 1991; McGechan and Wu, 2001)	$SS_{den} = 0 \quad \theta \leq \theta_d$ $SS_{den} = k_{den} \times 1.07^{(T-T_{opt})} \frac{\theta - \theta_d}{\theta_{fc} - \theta} C_{NO} \quad \theta_d \leq \theta \leq \theta_s$ $\theta_d = 0.627\theta_{fc} - 0.0267 \frac{\theta_s - \theta}{\theta_s} \theta_{fc}$	(120)
Root uptake of Nitrogen	$S_{upNH} = K_{r,NH} S_r C_{NH}$ $S_{upNO} = K_{r,NO} S_r C_{NO}$	(121)
Nitrogen losses to artificial drainage	$S_{drNH} = S_{dr} C_{NH}$ $S_{drNO} = S_{dr} C_{NO}$	(122)

In table 4, k_{nit} , and k_{den} , are respectively the optimal first-order rate coefficients for nitrification of N-NH₄, and denitrification of N-NO₃; T is the actual soil temperature (°C); T_{opt} is the optimum temperature for the process (°C) (Cabon et al., 1991); θ_d is the threshold water content for denitrification.

$K_{r,NH}$ and $K_{r,NO}$ are the root uptake preference factors (dimensionless) for either the N-NH₄ or the N-NO₃, accounting for positive or negative selection of solute ions relative to the amount of soil water that is extracted (van Dam et al., 1997). For passive uptake, $K_r=1$.

S_r and S_{dr} are the source-sink terms related respectively to root uptake and artificial drainage respectively, and θ_{fc} is the water content at field capacity (assumed as the water content at pressure head $h=-330$ cm in water column).

As for phosphorus, FLOWS describes the fate of liquid phase phosphorus (P_{liq}) according to the decay reaction chains proposed by Mansell et al. (1977a). In general, inorganic P is rapidly converted from orthophosphate to less soluble forms. Phosphorus soil solution concentrations generally observed after inorganic P supply to the soil are of the order of 1µg/cm or less (Mansell et al., 1977b). The initial rapid removal of phosphorus from the soil solution may be attributed to relatively fast reactions, such as physical adsorption to soil colloidal material. The adsorption of P is usually considered to be reversible (Van der Zee and Van Riemsdijk, 1986; Barrow et al., 1981). Other additional much slower reactions involve precipitation of phosphorus as Al, Fe, and Ca phosphates. Also, a portion of the physically adsorbed phosphorus may slowly become surrounded by matrices of Fe and Al components and become occluded (chemisorption). Mechanisms of adsorption, precipitation, and chemical immobilization operate simultaneously and continuously with time to remove phosphorus from the soil solution.

The Mansell et al. (1977a) approach, also adopted in FLOWS, assumes the transfer of phosphorus between solution, adsorbed, chemisorbed and precipitated to be controlled by six reversible reactions (see the block in the figure 12 about *Liquid phase phosphorus transformation process constants and pools in FLOWS*). While adsorption occurs on pore walls and colloids, chemisorption (also defined occlusion by the Mansell et al., 1977) refers to (slow) transformation of weaker physical bonds of the adsorbed phosphorus to stronger chemical bonds. FLOWS assumes adsorption to follow a Nth order kinetic (with an average N of 0.35, as suggested by Mansell et al., 1977a) and a constant K_{ads1} , whereas all the other reactions (desorption, chemisorption and mobilization, precipitation and dissolution) follow a first order kinetic, respectively with constants K_{ads2} , K_{chs1} , K_{chs1} , K_{prc1} , K_{prc2} , even if higher order may easily be developed in the code. Reactions rates depend on pH, nature and content of clay minerals, organic matter, carbonates, cation saturation and amount of phosphate applied. The table 5 summarises the equations controlling the liquid phase phosphorus transformation processes considered in FLOWS.

The remaining P-PO4 concentrations are thus transported through soil by advection-dispersion (subscript *transp* in figure 12):

$$\frac{\partial \theta C_P}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial q C_P}{\partial z} + \frac{\left(\partial \theta D \frac{\partial C_P}{\partial z} \right)}{\partial z} - S_{S_P} \quad (123)$$

with S_{S_P} being the sum of adsorption, desorption, precipitation, dissolution, root uptake, drainage losses and fertilizer (organic/inorganic) components:

$$S_{S_P} = -S_{S_{minP}} - S_{S_{firtP}} - \theta (K_{ads1} C_P^N + K_{prc1} C_P) + \rho_b (K_{ads2} C_{a,P} + K_{prc2} C_{p,P}) + S_{S_{upP}} + S_{S_{drP}} \quad (124)$$

In the equation 124, as well as in the equations in the table 5, subscript P is for P-PO4, whereas subscripts a , p and c are respectively for adsorbed, precipitated and chemisorbed phosphorus concentrations.

As for nitrogen, the source terms $S_{S_{minP}}$ and $S_{S_{firtP}}$, are obtained by dividing the mineralization rate and mineral phosphorus fertilizer addition rates (all in g/cm² of soil per day) by the incorporation depth, z_{fert} (cm), to obtain the corresponding S_s terms (in g/cm³ of soil per day) to be added to each of the calculation nodes within z_{fert} .

Table 5. The phosphorus transformation processes implemented in FLOWS (Mansell et al., 1977a). In the table, the S_s reaction rates are in g/cm^3 of soil per day

Phosphorus adsorption	$S_{S_{ads}} = \frac{\partial(\rho_b C_{a,P})}{\partial t} = K_{ads1} \theta C_P^N - (K_{ads2} + K_{chs1}) \rho_b C_{a,P} + K_{chs2} C_P$	(125)
Phosphorus chemisorption	$S_{S_{chs}} = \frac{\partial(\rho_b C_{c,P})}{\partial t} = K_{chs1} \rho_b C_{a,P} - K_{chs2} \rho_b C_{c,P}$	(126)
Phosphorus precipitation	$S_{S_{prc}} = \frac{\partial(\rho_b C_{p,P})}{\partial t} = K_{prc1} \theta C_P - K_{prc2} \rho_b C_{p,P}$	(127)
Root uptake of Phosphorus	$S_{upP} = K_{r,p} S_r C_P$	(128)
Phosphorus losses to artificial drainage	$S_{S_{drP}} = S_{dr} C_P$	(129)

4.3.2. Simulating only Nitrogen transport

FLOWS allows to simulate only nitrogen transport by partly following the empirical approach adopted in the RISK-N model (Gusman and Marino, 1999) for the mineralization of organic nitrogen. In this case, soil organic N is conceptually divided into active and passive fractions (Gusman and Marino, 1999). The active fraction includes organic N involved in the process of mineralization and is divided into rapid and slow mineralization fractions. The rapidly mineralizing N consists of recent additions of manure and crop residue. The slow fraction consists of resident soil N still mineralizing, as well as the remaining organic N from past manure and crop residue applications.

As for the previous case, the model handles additions of nitrogen in the forms of manure, crop residue, mineral fertilizers. The model requires the incorporation depth (called z_{fert} in the FLOWS code) as input. It is assumed that nitrogen addition is distributed uniformly along the incorporation depth. The model assume that manure applications contain 50% of urea and 50% of organic N. As for crop residues incorporation, it is assumed that 50% consists of rapidly mineralizing fraction, 45% of slowly mineralizing organic N and 5% is considered as passive fraction (Gusman and Marino, 1999).

Again, the mineralization process is assumed to be described by a first-order decay equation (Stanford and Smith, 1972; Watts and Hanks, 1978):

$$rNH4_{min} = k_{mOM}NOM_0 \exp(-k_{mOM}t) \quad (130)$$

with $rNH4_{min}$ the rate of N-NH₄ production from mineralization (g/cm² of soil per day), NOM_0 the initial pool of nitrogen in organic matter and k_{mOM} is a first order rate constant for the mineralization process. Now, the latter does not depend on the C/N ratio but still depends on soil temperature and water content, being a function of microbial processes. Also, as the mineralization rates change according to the type of organic N pools to be mineralized (rapid or slow), two different equations can be used to determine k_{mOM} in equation 130 (Kersebaum and Richter, 1991):

$$k_{mOM}(T) = k_{rp}(T) = 5.6 \times 10^{12} \exp\left(\frac{-9800}{T + 273}\right) F_w$$

$$k_{mOM}(T) = k_{sw}(T) = 4.0 \times 10^9 \exp\left(\frac{-8400}{T + 273}\right) F_w \quad (131)$$

where T is the actual soil temperature (°C) and the water content factor for mineralization, F_w , is calculated as in equation 99. For the calculation of $k_{rp}(T)$ and $k_{sw}(T)$, FLOWS uses the averages of both F_w and T within the incorporation depth, $zfert$.

Again, $rNH4_{min}$ is divided by $zfert$ to obtain the SS_{ftNH} .

As for immobilization, in this case FLOWS does not consider the C/N ratio but follows an empirical equation decay (Cabon et al., 1991):

$$\begin{aligned}
 SS_{imm} &= k_{im} \times 1.05^{(T-T_{opt})} F_w C_{NO} & \theta \leq \theta_{fc} \\
 SS_{imm} &= k_{im} \times 1.05^{(T-T_{opt})} \frac{1}{F_w} C_{NO} & \theta > \theta_{fc}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{132}$$

with a decay constant k_{im} and where T_{opt} is the optimal temperature for the process. All the other processes (Urea hydrolysis; Ammonia volatilization (N-NH₄ to N-NH₃), Nitrification (N-NH₄ to N-NO₃); Denitrification (N-NO₃ to -N-N₂); Plant uptake; Drainage losses, are all described by using the equations already seen for the previous case.

Again, the transport of N-NH₄ and N-NO₃ is described by solving simultaneously the equations 116-117, with SS_{NO} term in equation 118 now including also the SS_{imm} losses.

As mentioned, FLOWS deals with water and nitrogen transformations and transport in an integrated way, so that at each simulation time step the water contents and fluxes calculated by solving the Richards equation are used as input for the nitrogen equations, as illustrated in the figure 1b.

4.4. Calculation of the Osmotic Potential for salinity stress

For the calculation of the salinity stress reduction factor, α_s , the model requires the osmotic potential, h_{os} , to be used in the Mass and Hoffman approach (Mass and Hoffman, 1977) and in the van Genuchten and Hoffman approach (van Genuchten and Hoffman, 1984), as well as in the combined approach.

The code uses the concentration coming from the ADE solution for the calculation of the h_{os} values in all the nodes.

Firstly, the code calculates the soil solution electrical conductivity, EC as

$$EC = C * \frac{10^6}{640}
 \tag{133}$$

with EC in dSm^{-1} and C in gcm^{-3} .

Thus, the osmotic potential, h_{os} , is obtained as:

$$h_{os} = 360EC \quad (134)$$

5. Benchmarking (intercode comparison)

The reliability of FLOWS in numerical simulations has been evaluated by comparing the model results to those coming from HYDRUS 1D simulation for a set of water flow and solute transport processes involving different top and bottom boundary conditions.

This intercode comparison is especially effective as both the models are based on the same fundamental equations to describe water flow (Richards equation) and solute transport (Advection-Dispersion equation). Both the codes use similar strategies to adapt time stepping to a convergence criterium, allowing the time step size to increase when the code converges rapidly and decrease when there are convergence problems. Both the codes allow to set the several top and bottom boundary conditions, both constant or variable over time: potential and fluxes at the upper boundary, potential, fluxes and hydraulic gradient at the bottom boundary. Initial conditions may be given as pressure heads, which can be either constant along the soil profile or variable node by node. They also allow to use both unimodal and bimodal hydraulic properties as input for different soil layers.

In the following, the handbook provides a comparison between FLOWS and HYDRUS 1D results for a simulation carried out under real, quite complex, soil-groundwater-climatic conditions. The table 6 summarizes the top and bottom boundary conditions and soil and vegetation parameters used for the intercode benchmarking simulations (both for FLOWS and HYDRUS).

Table 6. Water and solute top and bottom boundary conditions and soil and vegetation parameters used for the intercode benchmarking simulations

		WATER		SOLUTE						
Top Boundary Atmospheric	variable	flux (cm/d)	pulse	Concentration (g/cm ³)	0.04					
				pulse duration (d)	1					
Top boundary irrigation	variable	flux (cm/d)		Concentration (g/cm ³)	0					
Bottom Boundary	variable	pressure head (cm)		constant	Concentration (g/cm ³)	0				
Initial condition	constant	pressure head (cm)	-100.00	constant	Concentration (g/cm ³)	0				
SOIL										
Layers in the soil profile	4									
Hydraulic properties Model	van Genuchten-Mualem									
Layer depths and hydraulic parameters										
layer	depth from the soil surface (cm)	bulk density	θ_s	θ_r	αVG	nvG	K0	tau		
1	40	1.67	0.361	0.017	0.033	1.187	118.080	0.500		
2	60	1.74	0.316	0.047	0.033	1.187	429.372	0.500		
3	100	1.78	0.309	0.047	0.033	1.187	479.961	0.500		
4	140	1.83	0.298	0.049	0.033	1.187	360.845	0.500		
VEGETATION										
Root distribution	Uniform									
Water Uptake reduction function	Feddes									
Feddes parameters for water uptake reduction	hI	hII	hIIIH	hIIIL	hIV					
	-1	-10	-400	-600	-8000					
Extinction factor for LAI	0.5									

The following figures provide a graphical view of the time-variable top and bottom boundary conditions, as well as of the time-variable vegetation conditions used for the simulation

Figure 13. Graphical view of the time-variable top and bottom boundary conditions, as well as of the time-variable vegetation conditions used for the simulation

The following figures present a comparison of key variables simulated by the two models under identical conditions (see table 6). Specifically, the figures illustrate evapotranspiration fluxes, as well as water fluxes, pressure heads, and solute concentrations at a depth of 20 cm, as predicted by the FLOWS model (solid orange lines) and the HYDRUS model (blue open circles).

Figure 14. Evapotranspiration fluxes, as well as water fluxes, pressure heads, and solute concentrations at a depth of 20 cm, as predicted by the FLOWS model (solid orange lines) and the HYDRUS model (blue open circles).

The graphs in figure 15 were obtained under the same scenario as before but assuming free drainage (unit hydraulic gradient) at the bottom boundary and a bare soil (no vegetation). Again, the solid lines are for FLOWS predictions whereas blue circles are for HYDRUS simulations.

Figure 15. Evapotranspiration fluxes, as well as water fluxes, pressure heads, and solute concentrations at a depth of 10 cm, as predicted by the FLOWS model (solid orange lines) and the HYDRUS model (blue open circles).

It is important to note that some flux peaks are missing in the HYDRUS results. This is due to the fact that HYDRUS outputs were recorded at two-day intervals, as HYDRUS-1D imposes a limitation on the number of output time steps that can be saved (250), whereas FLOWS outputs were generated at daily scale (365 printed times for one year simulation). Additionally, some of the (minor) discrepancies between the two simulations may be attributed to differences in how the two models construct the simulation flow fields, so that the node depths may not correspond exactly between FLOWS and HYDRUS. Some differences in evapotranspiration fluxes may be due to slight variations in how the two models handle surface evaporation and root water uptake across different nodes.

In any case, in general, it is important to recognize that simulations derived from the numerical solution of differential equations are inherently sensitive to the numerical strategies employed. Each model adopts its own discretization schemes and solution algorithms which, while conceptually aligned, often differ in implementation details. As a result, exact agreement between different models should not be expected.

6. Multisite simulations

FLAWS allows for simulations in multiple profiles (multi-site simulations). For each simulation profile, the model produces a set of outputs and store them in a specific folder. At the end of the multiple simulations, the model calculates two additional folders, respectively with the average and with the variance of the values of each output variable. The model also produces an output with a list of the failed simulations (with the corresponding failure flag related to convergence problems). The multi-site configuration may be especially useful in the following cases:

1. Simulations to be carried out on several soil profiles in a large area characterized by a spatial variability of the soil hydraulic properties. This may be required, for example, to calculate distributed outputs, such as (among many others): i. irrigation needs at district scale; ii. deep percolation fluxes of water and solutes to analyse groundwater recharge and/or groundwater vulnerability; iii....
2. Uncertainty Analyses and/or Sensitivity Analysis requiring simulation to be carried several times with different soil hydraulic parameters coming from probability density functions for each of them.

APPENDIX A. User instruction

A.1. Launching FLOWS

FLOWS operates within a MATLAB environment and is accessible through a dedicated web interface: <https://flows.unica.it/>

For user accessibility, a **client-server architecture** has been implemented. This allows users to interact with the model directly from their browser, without requiring local installations or configurations. The server executes the MATLAB routines and handles all the computational load, while the client interface provides a simple and intuitive access point.

Upon accessing the FLOWS website, users can authenticate with their personal login credentials. Once logged in, two options are available:

- **Start a new FLOWS project**, initializing a fresh simulation setup.
- **Load an existing project**, retrieving previously saved configurations and results (see Figure i).

The architecture is designed to separate clearly the **user interaction layer** (web front-end built on Vue.js) from the **computational engine** (MATLAB running on the server). Communication between the two layers is managed through dedicated APIs that ensure reliable data transfer, project persistence, and monitoring of the simulation status.

Projects and results will be stored on the server in a future release, allowing users to resume work at any time and from any device. At the current stage, this functionality is still under development. Simulation progress and outputs (soil water content, pressure heads, solute concentrations, evapotranspiration, etc.) are displayed in real time via the interface, while detailed result files remain available for download.

This architecture guarantees:

- **Accessibility**: no need for local MATLAB licenses or configuration.
- **Scalability**: server-side resources can be adapted to handle multiple simultaneous users.
- **Reproducibility**: all project data remain stored and versioned on the server.
- **Security**: access is restricted to authorized users through individual login credentials.

Figure i. Web window to start FLOWS

A.2. Instructions for FLOWS graphical interface users

In the case of a new project, the user will be asked to fill in seven blocks (plus a block to set the Units) (see the left part of the figure ii);

1. Simulation settings;
2. Node settings;
3. Top and bottom boundary conditions settings;
4. Time settings;
5. Solute settings (including a sub-block for Nitrogen Transport);
6. Vegetation settings;
7. Drainage settings.

Figure ii. Simulation settings block

The graphical interface will guide the user through the input process step by step, allowing each section to be completed sequentially. After configuring the Simulation Settings, the "Next" button will unlock access to the Nodes section, and so on.

A detailed description and explanation of the settings of each of the six blocks is given below.

A.2.1. Simulation Settings

This block contains six different menus:

Simulation menu

The model can be used in a "point-based" configuration, which allows for the analysis of flow and transport processes at a local scale (e.g., localized pollution), or in a "distributed configuration", which enables multi-site simulations. This is particularly important for applications such as irrigation planning and management at the sector or district scale, or for assessing the vulnerability of groundwater to diffuse pollution (e.g., from agricultural sources)

The simulation drop-down menu allows to opt for single or multiple simulations:

Single site = allows for a single simulation and the parameters are read from the profile settings;

Multisites = allows for multiple simulations for multiple sites. In this case, the user will be asked to set the number of profiles to be simulated and to upload the hydraulic parameters, as well as the climatic and vegetation parameters, for each of the sites to be simulated.

Solute transport menu

This menu considers four options to account or not for the solute transport:

no = solute transport is not simulated;

yes - ADE = solute transport is simulated by the Advection-Dispersion equation, according to the *Solute Transport settings* (see below). This option is for the case of a single solute transport;

yes - ADE nitrogen = this option allows for only nitrogen transformation and transport simulations by solving the Advection-Dispersion equation twice, once for N-NH₄ and once for N-NO₃, with appropriate exchange and source-sink terms, according to the procedure described in the section

4.3.2. Simulating only nitrogen transport;

Yes - ADE C-N-P = this option allows for carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus transformation and transport, according to the transformation-transport chain described in the section 4.3.1.

Simulating Organic Matter decomposition and Carbon, Nitrogen and Phosphorus transport

In the case the option *yes - ADE* is selected, an ADE settings block shows up allowing for selecting options for *decay* and *adsorption*:

Decay:

- *no* = solute decay is not simulated;
- *yes* = in the case of *Single site* simulation, a specific column will be added to the node conditions input (see the section on the node settings below) allowing the user to input a decay coefficient (one for each of simulated nodes). In the case of *Multi-site* simulation, the user will be asked to input a decay value for each of the soil layers in each of the sites to be simulated. In this case, a column for decay will be added to the profile settings table reporting the parameters for all sites.

Adsorption:

- *no* = adsorption is not simulated;
- *yes - linear* = adsorption is simulated by assuming a linear adsorption isotherm;
- *yes - Freundlich* = adsorption is simulated by assuming a Freundlich adsorption isotherm.

Irrigation menu

This menu contains four options:

no (only rainfall) = no irrigation. Rainfall is the only inflow allowed;

yes (computed by the model) = Irrigation fluxes are calculated by the model according to the criterium described in the section 2.6 *Irrigation*;

yes (given by the user) = Irrigation fluxes are calculated by the irrigation volumes actually supplied by the farmer. With this option, a specific column, labelled as *TBirr (top boundary irrigation)*, will automatically show up in the *time conditions* table (see the *Time settings* block);

yes (Daily ET requirements) = Irrigation fluxes are calculated as the potential evapotranspiration daily losses.

In the case the *yes (computed by the model)* option has been selected, the following window will show up:

The screenshot shows the 'Irrigation settings' window in the FLOWS software. On the left is a teal sidebar with navigation options: Simulation, Nodes, Boundaries, Time, Solute, and Settings. The main content area is white and contains the following settings:

- Uniformity coefficient:** Input field with value 0,75.
- Irrigation system:** Drop-down menu with 'Drip' selected.
- Average threshold pressure head allowed in the root zone:** Input field with value -500.
- Irrigation depth:** Input field with value 30.
- Number of irrigation intervals:** Drop-down menu with '3' selected.

Below these settings is a section titled 'Starting and ending for each irrigation interval' with a table:

	Start day	End day
Irrigation interval 1	189	217
Irrigation interval 2	0	0
Irrigation interval 3	0	0

Figure iii. Window for irrigation settings

This window allows the user to set:

- the distribution uniformity coefficient. The gross irrigation calculated by the model, multiplied by this coefficient, will give the net irrigation fluxes applied by FLOWS;
- the irrigation system. This is important in the case the option for rain interception by vegetation (see the vegetation settings block) will be selected. The drop-down menu includes the following choices: 1) Drip; 2) Sprinkler; 3) Surface irrigation.
- the *threshold pressure* (the critical pressure h_{crit}). This is the pressure head below which the “model irrigates” (see the section 4.1. **Irrigation** in the handbook);

- the *irrigation depth*, that is the depth over which the h_{av} , to be compared to h_{crit} , is computed by the model. The *irrigation depth* may be set at any value even if a reasonable value should be the maximum root depth D_r ;
- the *irrigation intervals*. Up to five periods may be selected, by entering the initial and final time for each interval. This is to allow the user to account for specific irrigation habits of farmers, who, for example, are used to stress the crop in some of the growth stages to improve organoleptic properties of the crop. By leaving the model “to irrigate” anytime $h_{av} < h_{crit}$, would not allow for considering the specific farmer behaviour.

Temperature menu

This menu considers two options to simulate or not the temperature:

no = the temperature is not simulated;

yes = the temperature is simulated according to the combined approach provided by van Wijk and De Vries (1963), based on the superposition of the annual and daily sinusoidal fluctuation around a constant value of the soil. In this case a Temperature settings window will show up and the user will be asked to set the following temperature simulation parameters:

	Annual value	Daily value
T_Av	12	
A_T	7	10
t_Tmax	0,5	200
tau	1	365
D_T	170	170
td0		1

Figure iv. The *Temperature settings* block

where the user is required to set the parameters:

- the *average annual temperature*, $T_{av,y}$ (°C);

- the daily and annual amplitudes, $A_{T,d}$ and $A_{T,y}$ (°C) of the sine wave oscillating around the average daily, $T_{av,y}$, and annual, $T_{av,y}$, temperature;
- the daily, $t_{Tmax,d}$, and annual $t_{Tmax,y}$, time (days) when the temperature reaches the maximum.
- The diurnal, $\tau=1$, and annual, $\tau=365$, wave period;
- The soil thermal diffusivity, D_T , ($\text{cm}^2\text{day}^{-1}$), that is, the ratio of the soil thermal conductivity to the soil volumetric heat capacity for the day ($D_{T,d}$) or the year ($D_{T,y}$);
- The day of the year, t_{d0} , (from 1 to 365) corresponding to the time $t = 0$ of the simulation.

In the case of either nitrogen transformation and transport simulation (*solute transport = yes, ADE - nitrogen*) or carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus transformation and transport simulation (*solute transport = yes ADE C-N-P*) the temperature is set to *yes* and the temperature setting window automatically shows up. Also, the time units are automatically set to *days*.

Vegetation menu

This menu considers two options to account or not for the presence of vegetation:

no = the evapotranspiration is not simulated. The upper boundary condition has to be imposed by the user either in terms of flux or pressure head. This is the case for example of simulations of laboratory experiments carried out under controlled top boundary conditions;

yes = the presence of vegetation is simulated according to the Vegetation settings (see later). The case of the bare soil is a special case of this option. In this case, the *LAI* and D_r columns in the time conditions have to be set to zero and the K_c has to be set at the bare soil value to convert the ET_r (the reference evapotranspiration) to the potential evaporation, E_p , from a bare soil.

Drain menu

This menu considers two options to account or not for the presence of artificial drainage:

no = the artificial drainage is not simulated;

yes = the presence of artificial drainage is simulated by applying the Hooghoudt's approach.

A.2.2. Nodes Params Settings

This block contains information about the flow field discretization and the initial conditions for simulation.

The block allows to define the soil profile in terms of number of layers and their corresponding hydraulic properties, as well as the initial conditions for water flow simulations.

The block includes constant option input boxes and two sub-blocks: *Nodes Parameter settings* (figure v-vi) and *Profile settings* (figure vii).

Figure v. The *node settings* block

The options to be set are:

number of nodes = it is set at 100 by default but any number of nodes may be set by the user;

inhin = index for the initial pressure head condition. It allows to set the initial conditions along the soil profile as:

constant = pressure head set at the value *hin* in all the profile nodes; the *hin* input box shows up, allowing the user to set the constant initial pressure head;

variable = pressure heads read from the *Node settings* table in the same block); the *hin* input box disappears and the user is asked to fill in a specific column in the Nodes table, with variable pressure head values for each of the nodes.

hin = initial pressure head in the case of *inhin* = constant

Node setting table = the table includes different columns for:

- *Node* number;
- *hin* = Variable pressure head values, in the case of *inhin* = variable;
- *Cin* = initial solute concentration, in the case of single solute transport simulation (*solute* = *yes* - *ADE*). In the case of *solute* = *yes* - *Nitrogen* and *solute* = *yes* - *CNP*, specific columns will show up for *Cin-NH4* and *Cin-NO3* (*solute* = *yes* - *Nitrogen*) or *Cin-NH4*, *Cin-NO3* and *Cin-*

PO4 (*solute = yes - CNP*); Also, columns will also add for setting immobilization (*Kimm*), nitrification (*Knitr*) and of denitrification (*Kdntr*) and denitrification constants, to be set node by node (see figure vi);

- *lambda* = dispersivity, λ , for each node, in the case of solute transport simulation;
- *decay* = decay coefficient, μ , for each node in the case of single solute transport simulation.

Figure vi. The node settings block in the case of nitrogen transport

The user may change any of the values in the table and save the modified table as an excel file (Save as XLSX).

Also, the user may upload a table previously saved as an excel file (Choose File).

As for the *Profile settings* sub-block (see figure vii), the user sets the following options:

Figure vii. The *profile settings* window

Model menu

This menu allows for selecting one of the following models for hydraulic properties:

- *Unimodal van Genuchten* = van Genuchten model for water retention and Mualem model for hydraulic conductivity;
- *Bimodal Durner* = Durner model for water retention and Mualem model for hydraulic conductivity;
- *Bimodal Ross & Smettem* = Ross and Smettem model for water retention and Mualem model for hydraulic conductivity;
- *Unimodal Gardner & Russo* = Russo model for water retention and Gardner model for hydraulic conductivity.

Vogel scaling pressure head = the pressure head to scale the van-Genuchten hydraulic properties close to saturation according to the modified van Genuchten model as modified by Vogel et al., (2001). This input box will show up only in the case of van Genuchten-Mualem model selection. By setting the value at zero, FLOWS will use the unmodified van Genuchten-Mualem model;

hfc = pressure head at field capacity. It will be used in the case the *irrigation computed by the model* has been set, as well as in the case of *solute – ADE* and *solute CNP options*

number of layers = number of horizontal layers in the soil profile.

Profile settings table: The table allows for setting the parameters of the hydraulic properties model selected for each layer.

The profile setting table contains a number of lines equal to the number of layers and a number of columns variable according to the selected model. For each layer a line shows the following variables:

layer = the layer in the soil profile;

depth = depth of the layer (the value for the last layer corresponds to the maximum depth of the simulated flow field);

rho = bulk density;

tetas = saturated water content;

tetar = residual water content;

The other parameters may change according to water retention and hydraulic conductivity models

Unimodal van Genuchten water retention:

alfvg = α_{VG} of the unimodal water retention function;

en = n of the unimodal water retention function;

Bimodal Durner water retention:

fi = weight for macroporosity;

alfvg = α_{VG1} for macroporosity;

en = n_1 for macroporosity;

alfvg2 = α_{VG2} for matrix;

en2 = n_2 for matrix;

Ross and Smettem water retention

fi = weight for macroporosity;

alfrs = α_{RS} for macroporosity;

en2 = n for the matrix;

alfvg2 = α_{VG} for the matrix;

Unimodal Russo water retention:

alfgr = α_{GR} of the unimodal water retention function;

mu = μ_R of the unimodal water retention function.

Hydraulic conductivity models

$K0$ = saturated hydraulic conductivity for the *unimodal van Genuchten*, *bimodal Durner*, *bimodal Ross and Smettem* and *unimodal Russo*

$bita$ = exponent in the Mualem hydraulic conductivity model;

As for the *Node settings* table, the user may change any of the values in the table and save the modified table as an excel file. The user may also upload a table previously saved as an excel file.

It is also possible to load a previously saved parameter configuration by clicking the *load from file* button. If in the **Simulations settings** the option *multi-sites* has been selected, along with the solute option *yes - ADE*, two columns will be added to the table, reporting the dispersivity λ and the decay μ values (only if the option *decay - yes* has been chosen) for each of the layers in each simulation site.

A.2.3. Boundary conditions settings

This block includes two sub-blocks, one for Top Boundary and one for Bottom Boundary conditions, respectively (Figure viii). They allow for setting if the water and solute boundary (top, bottom) conditions are constant or variable, if the water boundary condition refers to either a head (Dirichlet) or flux (Newman) condition. In the case of constant water boundary conditions, there are input boxes to set the corresponding value for the pressure head or flux.

Figure viii. The *Top and Bottom Boundary* conditions block

***itopvar* menu**

It allows setting either constant or variable Top Boundary conditions for water flow simulation:
constant = the top boundary condition is constant over the whole simulation time;
variable = the top boundary condition is variable over the simulation time;

***itbc* menu**

It allows setting either flux or pressure head Top Boundary conditions for water flow simulation:
flux = the top boundary condition (constant or variable) is a flux (Newman) condition. Positive and negative values are respectively for upward and downward fluxes;
potential = the top boundary condition (constant or variable) is a pressure head (Dirichlet) condition;

In the case of constant top boundary condition, the user has to set one of the following values, depending on the selected *itbc* option, in the corresponding input box:

hsurf = the pressure head value imposed at the soil surface (top boundary);

qsurf = the flux value imposed at the soil surface (top boundary).

In the case of *itbc* = *flux*, the user has also to set the value in the following input box:

hsurfmax = maximum value of the pressure head at the soil surface in the case of ponding formation during the simulation. This value is used in the code for calculating the maximum flux

(*fluxsurfmax*) at the soil surface. If *qsurf* exceeds the *fluxsurfmax*, the difference *qsurf - fluxsurfmax* will be considered runoff. When this condition occurs, the code switches the *itbc* condition from flux to pressure head at the *hsurfmax* value. In the case of *itopvar = constant*, this condition will be kept for the remaining simulation time; in the case of *itopvar=variable* this condition will be kept until the *qsurf* at the next input time becomes lower than the *qsurf* at previous time that has induced the runoff.

***ibotvar* menu**

It allows setting either constant or variable Bottom Boundary conditions for water flow simulation:

constant = the bottom boundary condition is constant over the whole simulation time;

variable = the bottom boundary condition is variable over the simulation time;

***ibbc* menu**

It allows setting either flux or pressure head Bottom Boundary conditions for water flow simulation. *flux* = the bottom boundary condition (constant or variable) is a flux (Newman) condition. Positive and negative values are respectively for upward and downward fluxes;

potential = the bottom boundary condition (constant or variable) is a pressure head (Dirichlet) condition;

gradient = the bottom boundary condition is set at a constant hydraulic head gradient, $dH/dz=const.$;

seepage = the bottom boundary condition is set a zero flux until the bottom boundary will saturate. During the simulation run, the model verifies if the pressure head at the bottom becomes zero or higher than zero. In that case, the model switches to a zero-head boundary condition.

In the case of constant bottom boundary condition, the user has to set one of the following values, depending on the selected *ibbc* option, in the corresponding input box:

hbot = the pressure head value imposed at the simulated profile bottom (bottom boundary);

qbot = the flux value imposed at the simulated profile bottom (bottom boundary).

When the gradient option has been selected, the following input box will automatically show up:

grad = the gradient value (generally 1, even if any gradient value may be set).

***iCtopvar* menu**

It shows up only in the case of solute transport simulations and allows setting either constant or variable Top Boundary conditions for solute transport simulation:

constant = the top boundary concentration is constant over the whole simulation time. In this case, the user will have to input the *solute pulse parameters* in the **Solute settings** block (see below);

variable = the top boundary concentration is variable over the simulation time. With this option, the user has to input the time variable concentrations in the table include in the **Time settings** block (see below).

A.2.4. Time settings

This block allows to set the following time parameters for simulations (see figure ix):

Figure ix. The *Time settings* block

dtin = initial simulation Δt ;

dtmin = minimum Δt allowed for simulation;

dtmax = maximum Δt allowed for simulation;

tmax = total simulation time;

The block also includes a table named *Time conditions*.

The table allows for setting the time variable conditions in terms of water and solute top and bottom boundary conditions, as well as for vegetation.

Depending on the simulation configuration set at the **Simulation Settings** block, the *Time conditions* window may contain a different number of columns:

Time conditions

Time	TBwat	TBirr	TBsol	BBwat	BBsol	ETr	Kc	LAI	Droot
0	-0.02	0	70	0	0.0995	0.0995	1	0.18	10
1	0	0	69.6	0	0.0995	0.0995	1.0031	0.18	10
2	0	0	69.2	0	0.0995	0.0995	1.0063	0.18	10
3	0	0	68.8	0	0.0995	0.0995	1.0094	0.19	10
4	0	0	68.4	0	0.0995	0.0995	1.0125	0.19	10
5	0	0	68	0	0.0995	0.0995	1.0156	0.19	10
6	-0.02	0	67.6	0	0.0995	0.0995	1.0188	0.19	10

Save as XLSX

Choose File

Figure x. The *time settings* window

1. *Time*;

and for each *Time*

2. *Top boundary water (TBwat)* (the *qsurf* or *hsurf* in this handbook text) = variable top boundary condition for water (flux, pressure head). *TBwat* will correspond to *qsurf* if *itbc=flux* and to *hsurf* if *itbc = potential*;
3. *Top boundary irrigation (TBirr)* (the *qirr* in the text) = variable irrigation fluxes at the soil surface;
4. *Top boundary solute (TBsol)* (*Cinput* in the text) = variable concentrations at the soil surface;
5. *Bottom boundary water (BBwat)* (the *qbot* or *hbot* in the text) = variable bottom boundary condition (flux, pressure head); *BBwat* will correspond to *qbot* if *ibbc=flux* and to *hsurf* if *ibbc = potential*. The column will not show up if *ibbc = grad*, in which case the *hbot* is calculated internally in the model according to the value set for *gradient* in the ***ibbc menu***;
6. *Bottom boundary solute (BBsol)* = variable concentrations at the bottom boundary;
7. *ET_r* = Reference Evapotranspiration
8. *Kc* = Crop coefficient;
9. *LAI* = Leaf Area Index.
10. *Droot* (*D_r* in the text) = Maximum depth of roots over time;

In the case of *solute - Nitrogen* or *solute - CNP* simulation, the following columns will add to the table

11. *Top boundary NH4 (TBNH4)* = variable NH4 concentrations at the soil surface;
12. *Top boundary NO3 (TBN03)* = variable NH4 concentrations at the soil surface;
13. *Top boundary P (TBPO4)* = variable PO4 concentrations at the soil surface;

14. *Bottom boundary NH4 (BBNH4)* = variable NH4 concentrations at the bottom boundary;
15. *Bottom boundary NO3 (BBNO3)* = variable NH4 concentrations at the bottom boundary;
16. *Bottom boundary P (BBPO4)* = variable PO4 concentrations at the bottom boundary;

Column 2 only shows up in the case of *itopvar = variable*;

Column 3 only shows up in the case of *irrigation = yes (given by the user)*;

Column 4 only shows up in the case of single solute simulation (*solute – ADE*) and *iCtopvar = variable*

Column 5 only shows up in the case of *ibotvar = variable* and/or *ibbc = flux or potential*;

Column 6 only shows up in the case of single solute simulation (*solute – ADE*) and either *qbot* (*itbc = 0*) or *hbot* (*itbc = 1*) are positive, which may require the concentration in the upward fluxes (in case of *qsurf > 0*) and the groundwater (in case of *hbot > 0*)

Columns 7 to 10 only show up in the case of *vegetation = yes*;

Columns 11 to 13 only show up in the case of *solute transport = yes – ADE nitrogen* or *solute transport = yes – ADE C-N-P*

Columns 6 and 14 to 16 only show up in the case of *solute transport = yes – ADE nitrogen* or *solute transport = yes – ADE C-N-P* and *qbot* (*itbc = 0*) or *hbot* (*itbc = 1*) are positive, as for column 6

In the case of no rainfall, the user has to set $TB_{wat}=0$ (The ET_r has to be added in a separate column)

Again, the user may change any of the values in the table and save the modified table as an excel file (Save as XLSX).

Also, the user may upload a table previously saved as an excel file (Choose File).

A.2.5. Solute settings

This block includes different settings for solute transport simulations (figure xi).

Figure xi. The *Solute settings* block

Solute transport = This input box is greyed out and simply recall the choice done in the Simulation Settings about the type of solute transport the user wants to carry out; The same if for the input boxes *iCtopvar* and *Adsorption*;

k_{run} = Mass transfer coefficient, controlling the solute fluxes from the surface soil layer to runoff;

K_H = *Henry constant*: It is the slope of the linear equilibrium relationship between gaseous, C_g , and liquid, C , concentrations.

Dzero = Diffusion coefficient in the liquid phase. It sets the molecular diffusion constant of the solute in bulk water. In the case of nitrogen transport simulation (*solute transport* = *yes - ADE nitrogen*), D_{0,NH_4} , D_{0,NO_3} and $D_{0,P}$ are set internally at the value of 1.61, 1.47 and 0.533 cm²/d,

respectively. D_{0,CO_2} is also calculated inside the code for each node as $D_{0,CO_2} = 0.8369 \cdot \exp(0.0269 \cdot T)$ (Engineering ToolBox, 2008. Gases Solved in Water - Diffusion Coefficients. (Available at: https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/diffusion-coefficients-d_1404.html);

D_{gs} = Dispersion coefficient in the gaseous phase for single solute transport;

Uptake factor (Kr) =. This input box refers to the solute uptake by roots. It sets the solute root uptake preference factor, in the equation 64. It accounts for positive or negative selection of ions relative to the amount of soil water extracted by roots.

Solute pulse sub-block: this part refers to the case of $iC_{topvar} = constant$ (if $iC_{topvar} = variable$, this sub-block will not show up):

tC_{input} = initial time of application of the solute pulse;

tC_{input_end} = end time of application of the solute pulse;

C_{input} = concentration of the solute pulse. The specific mass of solute, M_s [M/L²], applied during the time $tC_{input_end} - tC_{input}$, may be calculated as (see equation 68):

$$M_s = (q_{surf} + q_{irr}) \cdot C_{input} \cdot (tC_{input_end} - tC_{input})$$

where q_{surf} and q_{irr} are the fluxes at the top boundary coming from water rainfall (q_{surf}) and/or irrigation (q_{irr}).

Isotherm sub_block: This part allows to set the slope and the exponent of the solute adsorption isotherm (see equation 61 $C_{ad} = K_F C^p$)

These two input boxes named *slope* and *exponent* are related to the option selected in the ***solute transport menu*** described in the **Simulation Settings** section. If the selected option is *yes = ADE* and *adsorption = yes - linear*, only the input box *slope* will show up. In the case of *adsorption = yes - Freundlich*, the input box *exponent* will also show up to set the corresponding value.

Nitrogen, phosphorus and carbon transport sub-block

This sub-block includes the settings for either the Nitrogen transport (in the case of *solute transport = yes ADE Nitrogen* option) or of Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Carbon transport (in the case of *solute transport = yes ADE C-N-P* option) (see figure xii).

Figure xii. The *Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Carbon transport settings* sub-block (continued in figures xiii and xiv)

Under both the options, the user will be asked for setting the following parameters:

zfert = the incorporation depth of fertilizers. It is assumed that nitrogen addition is distributed uniformly along the incorporation depth (and thus uniformly distributed among the simulation nodes included in *zfert*);

T_{opt} = the optimum temperature for the immobilization, nitrification and denitrification processes;

Kh_{UR} = the first-order rate coefficients for the urea hydrolysis decay reaction;

Kv_{UR} = the first-order rate coefficients for the urea volatilization decay reaction;

The sub-block also includes a table named *Nitrogen and Phosphorus applications*. Preliminarily, the user has firstly to input the number of fertilizer applications in the input box *Fertilizers applications* (five in the window shown below). Thus, the user is asked to fill in the table (see figure xiii).

Nitrogen and Phosphorus applications

Fertilizer applications:

qtqstar_nit	MAN kg/ha	N-MAN kg/kg	P-MAN kg/kg	COV-CR kg/ha	N-COV-CR kg/kg	P-COV-CR kg/kg	UREA kg/ha	N-UREA kg/kg	NH4-SD kg/ha	N-NH4-SD kg/kg	NO3-SD kg/ha	P-SD kg/ha	P-P-SD kg/kg	NH4-FI kg/ha	N-NH4-FI kg/kg	NO3-FI kg/ha	N-NO3-FI kg/kg	P-F
55	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0.27	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
135	50000	0.003	0.002	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
175	0	0	0	0	0	0	200	0.46	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
273	30000	0.003	0.002	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
400	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	100	0.27	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Buttons: Save as XLSX, Choose File

Figure xiii. The *Nitrogen and Phosphorus applications* table

The window allows setting additions of nitrogen (in the solute transport = yes Nitrogen) and phosphorus (in the solute transport = yes CNP) in the forms of manure, crop residue, mineral fertilizers. All the applications are in kg/ha and are internally converted to g/cm².

The model requires the following inputs:

$qtqstar_nit$ = times of fertilizer applications;

MAN , $N-MAN$ and $P-MAN$ = manure amount in kg/ha and the nitrogen and phosphorus content in the fertilizer (kg/kg);

$COV-CR$, $N-COV-CR$ and $P-COV-CR$ = cover crop amount in kg/ha and the nitrogen and phosphorus content in the fertilizer (kg/kg);

$UREA$ and $N-UREA$ = urea amount in kg/ha and the nitrogen content in the fertilizer (kg/kg);

$NH4-SD$, and $N-NH4-SD$ = solid mineral ammonium fertilizer amount in kg/ha and the nitrogen content in the fertilizer (kg/kg);

$NO3-SD$ and $N-NO3-SD$ = solid mineral nitrate fertilizer amount in kg/ha and the nitrogen content in the fertilizer (kg/kg);

$PO4-SD$, and $P-PO4-SD$ = solid mineral phosphorus fertilizer amount in kg/ha and the phosphorus content in the fertilizer (kg/kg);

NH₄-FI and *N-NH₄-FI* = liquid (supplied by injection or fertigation, for example) mineral ammonium fertilizer amount in kg/ha and the nitrogen content in the fertilizer (kg/kg);
NO₃-FI and *N-NO₃-FI* = liquid (supplied by injection or fertigation, for example) mineral nitrate fertilizer amount in kg/ha and the nitrogen content in the fertilizer (kg/kg);
PO₄-FI, and *P-PO₄-FI* = liquid mineral phosphorus fertilizer amount in kg/ha and the phosphorus content in the fertilizer (kg/kg);

As for the previous tables, the user may change any of the values in the table and save the modified table as an excel file (Save as XLSX).

Also, the user may upload a table previously saved as an excel file (Choose File).

Isotherm parameters and kinetic constants (see figure xiv)

Figure xiv. The Isotherm parameters and kinetic constants settings

Isotherm parameters for both the NH₄ and the NO₃ nitrogen forms and for PO₄ (in the case of *solute transport = ADE C-N-P*): under both cases, the option *adsorption = yes – linear*, is automatically set and only the input box *slope* will show up, while the input box *exponent* will remain greyed out and fixed to 1. Note that the slope for phosphorus corresponds to the parameter K_{ads1} in figure 12.

$K_r = Uptake\ factor$ for NH₄, NO₃ and PO₄: These input boxes refer to the N-NH₄, N-NO₃ and PO₄ uptake by roots.

Kinetic constants for phosphorus. K_2 , K_3 , K_4 , K_5 and K_6 correspond respectively to K_{ads2} , K_{chs1} , K_{chs2} , K_{prc1} and K_{prc2} in figure 12. They represent the first order kinetic constant related to phosphorus reactions of desorption, chemisorption and mobilization, precipitation and dissolution, respectively.

A.2.6. Vegetation settings

This block contains the settings related to the vegetation (evapotranspiration, water and osmotic stresses, root distribution) (see figure xv).

Figure xv. The *vegetation parameters* window

Extinction factor for LAI = exponent of the Beer's law for separating potential evaporation and transpiration from total potential evapotranspiration;

Root uptake compensation = This menu considers two options to account or not for the root uptake compensation in case of water and/or osmotic stresses:

no = compensation is not calculated;

yes = compensation is calculated according to the approach proposed by Jarvis (Jarvis, 1989); Šimůnek and Hopmans, 2008). The details are given in the section 2.1.2.3. *Root uptake compensation in case of water and osmotic stresses*. In this case, the following input box will show up:

omeg_c = critical stress index threshold, defining the T_a/T_p ratio at which reduced water uptake from stressed regions of the root zone is fully offset by increased uptake from less-stressed depth compartments in the root zone;

Water and Osmotic stress reduction functions for root uptake menu

This menu allows for selecting the type of reduction function for root water uptake related to either water stress, osmotic stress or both. In the latter case, the code assumes a multiplicative combination of water and salinity stresses.

- Feddes water reduction function
- van Genuchten water reduction function
- Mass & Hoffman salinity reduction function
- van Genuchten salinity reduction function
- Multiplicative van Genuchten water and salinity reduction function
- Multiplicative Feddes (water) and Mass & Hoffman (salinity) reduction function

The value in the following input boxes has to be set depending on the option selected for the stress reduction function:

Feddes water stress potentials

hI, hII, hIII, hIII, hIV = critical pressure heads for the Feddes water reduction function;

van Genuchten water stress parameters

hw50 = the soil water pressure head at which root water uptake is reduced by 50%

pw1 = a fitting parameter frequently assumed to be 3

van Genuchten salinity stress parameters

hs50 = the soil water osmotic potential at which root water uptake is reduced by 50%

ps1 = a fitting parameter frequently assumed to be 3

Mass & Hoffman salinity stress parameters

aMH = threshold osmotic potential value for the Mass and Hoffman salinity reduction function

bMH = slope of the Mass and Hoffman salinity reduction function

It should be noted that aMH and bMH parameterize local reductions in the root water uptake rate as a function of osmotic head. In this sense, they should not be confused with the parameters A and B frequently found in the literature and that parameterize total yield reductions as a function of average root zone salinity.

Depending on the water and salinity reduction functions selected, only the input boxes with the parameters actually involved in the simulation will show up. The other will be automatically greyed out

Root Distribution function menu

- *Uniform root distribution* (the distribution is just $1/D_{root}$ and does not need parameters to be input in this window);
- *Logistic root distribution*;
- *Prasad root distribution* (it is a triangular distribution and does not need parameters to be input in this window);
- *Vrugt distribution*

rda, rdb, rdc = *Logistic root distribution* parameters

$pz, zstar$ = *Vrugt root distribution* parameters

Note that, in the case of Vrugt root distribution, FLOWS sets $pz = 1$ for $z > zstar$ and $pz =$ the value provided by the user in the FLOWS input box for $z \leq zstar$.

Depending on the root distribution function selected, only the input boxes with the parameters actually involved in the simulation will show up.

Interception = This menu considers two options to account or not for the rainfall (atmospheric or from sprinkler irrigation):

no = interception is not calculated;

yes = interception is calculated according to the approach proposed by Von Hoyningen-Hüne (1983) and Braden (1985). In this case, an input box will show up, where the user has to input the empirical coefficient a_{int} involved in the interception equation. By default, this value is set at -0.025, which is a value frequently used for ordinary agricultural crops (Kroes et al., 2008).

A.2.7. Drainage settings block

This block allows setting the parameters used by the model for calculating the fluxes to artificial drains (both drain-pipes and open field drains) (see figure xvi).

Figure xvi. The *drainage settings* block

This window shows up only in the case the user has selected the option *drain = yes* in the **Simulation Settings** block.

In this case, the following input boxes will show up to set the required input parameters:

Ldr = drain distance;

zimp = the depth of the impermeable layer (from the soil surface);

zdr = depth of drainpipes installation or of the base of open drains;

Rdr = the hydraulic radius of the drain

A.2.8. Units

This block allows to set up the units for data and parameters used in the text. The code uses cm for length and g for mass. The time units have to be selected by the user as seconds, minutes, hours or days. These units will be used by the code to set the titles in the graphs generated by the code at the end of a simulation run (see the section below *Model outputs*)

A.2.9. Saving the project

Once all the different simulation blocks have been completed, after clicking the *Compute* button, FLOWS will generate a project with a predefined name, which can be changed by the user and then downloaded and saved by the user. This project can be loaded again by the user to modify it and run it again.

A.2.10. Multi-site simulations

In the case of a multi-site simulation, the user will be asked to specify the number of sites to be simulated. In this configuration, for each site, FLOWS requires the following input tables:

1. profile settings;
2. time settings;
3. vegetation settings;
4. fertilizers, if solute transport is set to *ADE Nitrogen* or *ADE CNP*.

As for the single site option, also in the *multi-site* case the number of columns showing up in the table will change according to the simulation configuration built by the user within the **Simulation Settings** block, with an additional column for the site identification.

For each of the table types, the model will generate a table reporting in vertical sequence the parameters/conditions corresponding to each site.

As an example, figure xvii shows the soil *profile settings* for a *multi-site* simulation. Compared to the single site, now the table includes a column named *Site* reporting in vertical sequence the site number.

The screenshot shows the FLOWS software interface. On the left, there is a sidebar with 'Simulation' and 'Nodes' tabs, and a 'Settings' icon at the bottom. The main area displays simulation parameters: 'Model' (set to 'Umsatz von Geruchten'), 'Vogel water retention scaling potential' (set to 0), 'hfc' (set to .333), and 'Number of layers' (set to 12). Below these settings is a small table with columns: Site, Layer, Depth, rho, tetas, tetar, and alfg. Below this table are 'Save as XLSX' and 'Choose File' buttons.

Site	Layer	Depth	rho	tetas	tetar	alfg	en	K0	bita
1	1	40	1.67	0.361	0.017	0.0334	1.187	118.08	0.5
1	2	60	1.74	0.3164	0.0469	0.0334	1.187	429.372	0.5
1	3	100	1.78	0.3091	0.0467	0.0334	1.187	479.9613	0.5
1	4	140	1.83	0.298	0.049	0.0334	1.187	360.8446	0.5
2	1	40	1.67	0.361	0.017	0.0334	1.187	118.08	0.5
2	2	60	1.74	0.3164	0.0469	0.0334	1.187	429.372	0.5
2	3	100	1.78	0.3091	0.0467	0.0334	1.187	479.9613	0.5

Figure xvii. The *profile settings* table for a multi-site simulation

For the same *multi-site* simulation, the figure xviii reports the table for *time settings*.

Figure xviii. The *time settings* table for a multi-site simulation

In the case of vegetation, besides the time variable conditions to be set in the time settings table (LAI , K_c , D_r , ...), the *multi-site* option requires the parameters for the extinction factor for the specific vegetation in the site, along with the water and/or the salinity stress, changing according to the reduction function selected (Feddes, van Genuchten, Mass and Hoffmann, ...) (see figure xix).

Figure xix. The *time settings* table for a multi-site simulation

Finally, figure xx shows how FLOWS build the table for fertilizers application under the multi-site case.

Figure xx. The *fertiliser settings* table for a multi-site simulation

In order to fill in the tables, the user may follow two different strategies. The first one is to fill in an excel file with different sheets, each reporting the table (profile, time, ...) for each site. By clicking on the *Choose file* button and uploading the file, the model will query the excel file and automatically build the table as shown in the previous figures.

Alternatively, the user may save the table, automatically generated by model while setting the different simulation options, as an excel file. In this case, the excel file will show the parameters/variables for the different sites in a vertical sequence within the same sheet, which can be modified by the user, saved and uploaded with the *Choose file* button below the table in the graphic window in it for the different sites.

A.3. Model output

At the end of the simulation FLOWS will produce a zipped folder that can be saved in any folder specified by the user. The output files include excel (xlsx) data.

The table i provides a list of the output files, with a description of the variables recorded in the output files:

Table i. Output of FLOWS

Output file	Output file	File content
<i>(instantaneous output)</i>	<i>(time-cumulative output)</i>	<i>(for all printing times. Only pote_tot reports the pressure heads for all the time steps in the simulation)</i>
pote_tot		Pressure heads (L) as a function of depth and time for all the simulation times
pote_print		Pressure heads (L) as a function of depth and time for printing times
teta_print		Water contents (L^3L^{-3}) as a function of depth and time for print times
cap_print		Water capacity (the derivative of the water retention curve) ($L^3L^{-3}L^{-1}$) as a function of depth and time for print times
flux_print	flux_cum	Water fluxes (LT^{-1}) as a function of depth and time for print times
sink_print	sink_cum	Sink (water uptake) (T^{-1}) as a function of depth and time for print times
sink_drain	sink_drain_cum	Artificial Drainage losses (T^{-1}) as a function of depth and time for print times
conc_print		Solute concentrations (ML^{-3}) as a function of depth and time for print times
conc_DR		Solute mass ($ML^{-2}T^{-1}$) leaving the soil profile by drainage as a function of depth and time for print times
conc_NH4_print		Ammonium nitrogen (N-NH4) solute concentrations (ML^{-3}) as a function of depth and time for print times

conc_NO3_print		Nitrate nitrogen (N-NH4) solute concentrations (ML ⁻³) as a function of depth and time for print times
conc_PO4_print		Phosphorus (P-PO4) solute concentrations (ML ⁻³) as a function of depth and time for print times
conc_CO2_print		CO2 mass (ML ⁻² T ⁻¹) produced in the soil profile by root and microbial respiration as a function of depth and time for print times
conc_NH4_DR		Ammonium nitrogen (N-NH4) mass (ML ⁻² T ⁻¹) leaving the soil profile by drainage as a function of depth and time for print times
conc_NO3_DR		Nitrate nitrogen (N-NO3) mass (ML ⁻² T ⁻¹) leaving the soil profile by drainage as a function of depth and time for print times
conc_PO4_DR		Phosphorus (P-PO4) mass (ML ⁻² T ⁻¹) leaving the soil profile by drainage as a function of depth and time for print times
flux_surf_bot	flux_surf_bot_cum	Water fluxes (LT ⁻¹) at top and bottom boundary as a function of time for print times
runoff	runoff_cum	Water and solute fluxes to runoff (LT ⁻¹) as a function of time for print times
qirr	qirr_cum	Irrigation fluxes (LT ⁻¹) (gross and net irrigation) for print times in the case of irrigation computed by the model

Figure xxi reports an example of output for all the printing times and the depths:

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	
Nodes	Depth\Time	0.01	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
1	1	0.690	0.296216583	0.290743987	0.289383195	0.288880161	0.288467821	0.288122145	0.287785949	0.288687446	0.28754289	0.287039947	0.286626733
2	2	2.069	0.297177107	0.291795204	0.290531601	0.290031168	0.28961936	0.289275388	0.288941231	0.289742186	0.28869826	0.288199497	0.287789264
3	3	3.448	0.297949159	0.292851038	0.291680444	0.291182786	0.290772662	0.290430095	0.290098075	0.290806328	0.289852916	0.289358922	0.288951866
4	4	4.828	0.298611884	0.293912539	0.292830632	0.292336384	0.291928514	0.291587293	0.291257258	0.291880057	0.291007825	0.290519146	0.290115412
5	5	6.207	0.299225277	0.294980719	0.293983062	0.293492933	0.293087681	0.292747804	0.292419527	0.292963573	0.292163926	0.291681043	0.291280728
6	6	7.586	0.299882263	0.296056584	0.295138624	0.294653271	0.294250912	0.29391237	0.293585614	0.294057097	0.293322141	0.292845455	0.292448614
7	7	8.966	0.300419234	0.297141146	0.296298204	0.295818188	0.295418949	0.29508171	0.294756244	0.29516087	0.294483373	0.294013201	0.29361985
8	8	10.345	0.301021762	0.29823541	0.297462682	0.296988461	0.296592535	0.296256538	0.295932138	0.29627516	0.295648509	0.295185084	0.294795205
9	9	11.724	0.301629408	0.299336354	0.298628831	0.298160679	0.297767929	0.297433029	0.297109416	0.297395672	0.296813767	0.296357148	0.295970617
10	10	13.103	0.302243671	0.300445198	0.299797801	0.299335902	0.298946186	0.298612215	0.298289121	0.298523025	0.29798033	0.297530506	0.297147179
11	11	14.483	0.302865348	0.301563116	0.300970721	0.300515177	0.30012834	0.299795115	0.299472279	0.299657848	0.299149348	0.298706246	0.298325963
12	12	15.862	0.30349489	0.302691237	0.302148705	0.301699537	0.301315416	0.300982737	0.300659906	0.300800787	0.300321945	0.299885437	0.29950802
13	13	17.241	0.304132591	0.303830639	0.303332852	0.302890007	0.302508429	0.302176083	0.301853006	0.301952506	0.301499225	0.301069128	0.300694384
14	14	18.621	0.304778676	0.304982352	0.304524249	0.304087611	0.303708391	0.303376148	0.303052578	0.303113685	0.302682274	0.302258361	0.301886084

Figure xxi. An example of an output file for all the printing times and all the depth nodes

In the matrix, the first two column report the simulation node and the corresponding depths of the simulation domain, whereas the first line reports the printing times. All the other values refer to the specific variable recorded in the file (potentials, sink, fluxes, ...)

Figure xxii reports an example of an output file for the top and boundary fluxes (named *flux_surf_bot*). In the file, the first column reports the title of printed variable. The first two lines reports the simulation time in terms, respectively, of number time steps (*j* in the time discretization used in the code) and corresponding print time. The other numbers represent:

- the fluxes passing through the soil surface (fluxsurf);
- the intercepted fluxes (flux_interc);
- the evaporation fluxes (flux_evap);
- the fluxes passing through the bottom of the simulated domain (fluxbot).

(Note that positive values are for upward fluxes and negative values are for downward fluxes).

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
time	0.01	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
fluxsurf	0.071769689	0.071769689	0.092056469	0.092343249	0.092214131	0.092499623	0.092785116	0.073070609	0.093356101	0.093641594	0.093927087	0.094212579
flux_interc	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
flux_evap	0.091769689	0.091769689	0.092056469	0.092343249	0.092214131	0.092499623	0.092785116	0.093070609	0.093356101	0.093641594	0.093927087	0.094212579
fluxbot	-1.258740387	-1.258740387	-1.258740387	-1.258740387	-1.258740387	-1.258740387	-1.258740387	-1.258740387	-1.258740387	-1.258740387	-1.258740387	-1.258740387

Figure xxii. An example of output file named *flux_surf_bot*

Figure xxiii reports an example of the output file named *runoff*.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1		30	69	83	89	108	117	135	144	149	154	161
2	time	0.01	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
3	qin	-0.02	-0.02	0	0	0	0	0	-0.02	0	0	0
4	fluxsurf	0.071769689	0.071769689	0.092056469	0.092343249	0.092214131	0.092499623	0.092785116	0.073070609	0.093356101	0.093641594	0.093927087
5	runoff	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
6	runsol_NH4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7	runsol_NO3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	runsol_PO4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure xxiii. An example of output file named *runoff*

The first column and the first two lines are as in the previous table. The other numbers represent respectively:

- the water fluxes applied at the top boundary (rainfall, irrigation, ...) (qin);
- the water fluxes passing through the soil surface (fluxsurf);
- the water fluxes to runoff (runoff);
- the solute fluxes to runoff (runsol, in the case of a single solute transport).

In the case of nitrogen and phosphorus transport:

- the N-NH4 solute fluxes to runoff (runsol_NH4);
- the N-NO3 solute fluxes to runoff (runsol_NO3).
- the P-PO4 solute fluxes to runoff (runsol_PO4)

FLOWS produces the *qirr* output file only in the case of the option *irrigation = yes* (computed by the model)

Additionally, at the end of the simulation, the interface allows users to query the output matrices in order to generate plots of output variables for user-selected times and depths.

The MATLAB data are used for graphical output, showing selected output variables at the end of each model run for selected times and depths (namely, water contents, pressure heads, concentrations, fluxes and eventual runoff).

Figure xxiv reports the FLOWS window allowing users to select specific times and depths at which to generate output graphs some examples of the graphs produced by the model.

Figure xxiv. The FLOWS window, allowing users to select specific times and depths at which to generate output graphs

Some examples of the graphs generated by the model are reported in the figures below (figures xxv-xxvii):

Figure xxv. Graphs generated by the model for pressure heads, water contents and water fluxes at three different depths

Figure xxvi. Graphs generated by the model for concentrations of NH₄, NO₃, PO₄ at three different depths

Figure xxvii. Graphs generated by the model for fluxes at soil surface and bottom boundary, evaporation and interception fluxes, water and solute fluxes to runoff

The user may decide the print times and the depths to be used in the plots (up to three times and depths).

A.3.1. Multiple sites configuration outputs

In the case the *multi-sites* configuration has been selected, the model will produce an output folder including a folder for each simulated site, containing the same outputs produced for the *single-site* configuration. Additionally, the model also produces two additional output folders, reporting

respectively the mean and variance of the output variables calculated for each site (see the following figure, providing an example of *multi-sites* simulation with 5 sites). The mean and the variance may be useful in the case of simulations carried out in a stochastic framework, where the different sites do not really correspond to spatially distributed points but may represent different hydraulic parameter vectors for a single simulation point, thus always with the same pedological profile.

At the end of the *multi-site* simulations, FLOWS will generate graphs with selected aggregate variables, such as cumulative evaporation and transpiration, water storage along the soil profile, cumulative water and solutes percolation at selected depths, cumulative water and solutes fluxes to the runoff,

As for the single site option, at the end of the simulation FLOWS will produce a zipped folder that can be saved in any folder specified by the user. This output folder will include as many sub-folders as the simulated sites, plus two subfolders for the average and the variance. As in the single site option, each of these subfolders output files include the excel (xlsx) data already shown in table i.

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